

**MINISTRY OF HIGHER AND SECONDARY SPECIALIZED
EDUCATION OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN**

**TASHKENT STATE PEDAGOGICAL UNIVERSITY NAMED AFTER
NIZAMI**

UDC: 42:494,375

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SAIDOVA MARIYA ALEKSANDROVNA

NONVERBAL ASPECTS OF INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION

**5A111401– Foreign languages and literature
(The English language)**

DISSERTATION

for academic Master's degree

Recommended for defense
Head of department "Theory and methodology
of teaching English language"

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Z.R. Abdujabborova

Scientific advisor: DSc, prof.

G.T. Makhkamova

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ANNOTATION

Goal of the research is the identification of cultural-semantic peculiarities of nonverbal means and working out ways of teaching nonverbal aspects of intercultural communication in English classes.

The novelty results of the research is seen 1) the theoretical assumptions of the nonverbal aspect of intercultural communication have been summarised; 2) comparative analysis of nonverbal means in English and Russian linguocultures has been conducted; 3) the materials, instructions and assessment tools to implement the created model have been worked out.

The proposed materials enable the development of students' intercultural communicative competence effectively with a focus on teaching nonverbal means of communication; the developed materials and assessment criteria can be used both at the Bachelor's and Master's departments of language universities; the materials allow improving the level of students' intercultural communicative competence.

Цель исследования заключается в выявлении культурно-семантических особенностей невербальных средств и разработки способов обучения невербальным аспектам межкультурной коммуникации на уроках английского языка.

Новизна исследования: 1) обобщены теоретические положения невербального аспекта межкультурной коммуникации; 2) проведен сравнительный анализ невербальных средств в английской и русской лингвокультуре; 3) разработаны материалы, инструкции и инструменты оценки для реализации созданной модели.

Предложенные материалы позволяют эффективно развивать межкультурную коммуникативную компетенцию студентов с акцентом на обучение невербальным средствам общения; разработанные материалы и критерии оценки могут быть использованы как для студентов бакалавриата, так и магистратуры языковых вузов; материалы позволяют повысить уровень межкультурной коммуникативной компетентности студентов.

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INTRODUCTION

Shavkat Mirziyoyev, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, signed the Resolution "On Measures for the Further Development of the Higher Education System" in Uzbekistan on April 20, 2017. This document was adopted with the goal of improving the higher education system, revising the content of specialist training in higher education to align with the country's priority socioeconomic development goals, and creating the necessary conditions for specialist training in higher education to meet international standards. The National model of training specialists has been created in Uzbekistan which is based on traditions of our people reflecting the centuries – old history development of Uzbek nation. Distinctive peculiarity of the National program is its purpose of training comprehensively developed personnel, mastering foreign languages and meeting the requirements of international standards of specialists training.

In this respect, it will be appropriate to cite the words of the president of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov, who said: “Our land produced outstanding scientists who are the pride of the whole world. We have all conditions to continue and enrich national traditions of scientific thinking established by them”.

On December 10, 2012 President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov signed a decree “On measures to further improve foreign language learning system”.

A great number of opportunities for learning foreign languages especially English in the republic of Uzbekistan are being created in the last four years. A lot of projects, various teaching methods with using modern and information technologies in education, which can motivate a new generation of youth to learning foreign languages have been implementing. At the same time movements in the system of training specialists who are confident in teaching foreign languages, actions in creating conditions and opportunities for wide use of sources have been developing in the country.

Topicality of the paper. Development of international relations in spheres of human activity such as politics, science, culture and economy require to communicate with representatives of other cultures and nations. The role and importance of fluently knowing foreign languages for our nation and country is considerable, which is peacefully making multilateral relations with the other nations of the world and is trying to have its` consequent place in the world community.

The practice of communication in English by nonnative students shows that they know language but haven't access knowledge about national-cultural specifics of nonverbal symbols. Revealing the national-cultural specific of nonverbal behavior is critically important because of it is subject of cultural diversity. In other words, culture is a large degree determines which posture, gesture, or interpersonal distance is appropriate in a host of social situations. This influence of culture on nonverbal behaviour can be considered from two perspectives: 1) determination of the specific nonverbal behaviours that represent or symbolize specific thoughts, feelings, or states of the communicator; 2) description of ways for acquiring nonverbal means for organization of productive intercultural communication.

Problem development status. Conceptual and applied aspects of inter/cross-cultural communication were studied by such scholars R.Scollon, M.Bennett, M.Byram, S.Ter-Minasova, and others. Intercultural dimensions for study the types of the culture were worked out by E.T.Hall., ; G.Hofstede, R.Lewis, Kluckhohn, S.Schwartz, H.Triandis, F.Trompenaars, F. and C. Hampden-Turner.

The local researchers like D.Ashurova, M.Djusupov, Sh.Safarov, D.Khashimova, A.Mamatov, G.Makhkamova, D.Abduazizova and others were also looking at different aspects of cross-cultural communication, the relation between language and culture from the linguistic and cognitive perspectives.

The issues of non-verbal semiotics are often discussed in academic (primarily linguistic) literature. Along the same lines, non-verbal communication is observed

from the psychological, psycholinguistics, and pedagogic standpoints by Potapova (1997), Melnik (2002), Borg (2011), Makhkamova (2012), Gorelov (2003), Abduazizova (1997).

One of the most striking works on our topic is the book by A. Pease, "Body language: how to read the thoughts of others by their gestures" [Pease, 2004]. His study includes gesture descriptions, origin, semantics addressing a wide range of readers. How wide is the range of addressees of such books on non-verbal communication, can be seen from the introduction to Paul Ekman's and Wallace Friesen's work "Unmasking the face: A guide to recognizing emotions from facial clues"[2010], that is directed to all specialist who has intercultural contacts.

The literature review shows that non-verbal communication from a linguistic standpoint is studied fruitfully and variedly. However, the study of verbal and non-verbal communication from the linguodidactic aspect of intercultural communication is an urgent problem and is far from the final resolution.

Goal of the research is identification of cultural-semantic peculiarities of nonverbal means and working out special ways of teaching nonverbal aspect of intercultural communication at English classes.

Objectives for achievement the pointed goal:

- to study the features of communicative and noncommunicative behavior;
- to deal with the main factors for organizing successful communication;
- to identify the types of nonverbal means and specify their cultural features in formal and functional levels;
- to reveal pragmatic difficulties in obtaining nonverbal means of communication:
- to design material for teaching nonverbal means of communication at English classes.

Object of the research is nonverbal means of intercultural communication of the English people.

Subject of the research is cultural-semantic peculiarities of nonverbal means of the English people and ways of teaching nonverbal aspect of intercultural communication at English classes.

Methods of the research: critical analysis of academic literature, description, distribution, cross-cultural analysis, summarizing the cultural experience in using nonverbal means, experiment and statistics.

Novelty of this study is seen in 1) conducting comparative analysis of nonverbal means in English and Russian linguocultures; 2) identification of cultural specificity of nonverbal means and difficulties for their interpretation and application; 3) creation of special technology of teaching nonverbal means at English classes.

Theoretical and practical values: complex study of nonverbal means from the position of semiotics, pragmatics and linguodidactics allows teachers to realizing their formal and functional aspects and importance of these means for organization of intercultural communication. Practical significance is the results of this study and created practical materials can be used in comparative linguistics, intercultural communication, linguistic country study and methodology of FLT.

The structure of the research. The MA dissertation consists of introduction, three chapters, conclusion, the list of the used literature and appendix.

CHAPTER I. THEORETICAL GROUNDS OF THE NONVERBAL ASPECT OF INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION

1.1. The problems of communicative and noncommunicative behaviours

Our primary concern is to consider the definition of the concept - behaviour. As nowadays, behaviour, being a complex phenomenon affecting to a large extent the social aspect of the life of society, is included in the sphere of research interests of such disciplines as functional stylistics, the culture of speech, rhetoric's, and many others. Fassnacht [2000], Furr [2009], I.A. Sternin [1989] and others try to develop this concept. The issues of choosing communicative and non-communicative behaviours in various situations on the scientists' screen more frequently than before. Currently, the problems of speech, communicative and non-communicative behaviour are developed from the linguistic anthropology standpoint. And they are investigated within the framework of such sciences as psycholinguistics, sociolinguistics, cultural linguistics and pragmalinguistics.

First of all, we would like to mention that researchers interpret the concept of behaviour in different ways. This diversity may be seen in analysing definitions from various fields and disciplines. We chose two of them based on recent reviews and built on more complex concepts than the usual simplistic definition of behaviour as actions or the way someone behaves.

Fassnacht, a German-speaking psychologist who specialises in behavioural research, defined behaviour as "those continuing activities of an organism or issuing from an organism that may be externally experienced" [Fassnacht, 2000. p. 195-198]. At the same time, Fassnacht emphasised that behaviour is a process, as opposed to talents or inclinations, which just facilitate behaviour. The term organism implies that behaviour is an universal concept of living creatures, but experiencing, thinking, and emotions are consciousness-carrying phenomenon that are not expected to be present in all types of organisms in the same way. Fassnacht stated that behaviour is not simply a research object, but it is also affected by human perception as well as may thus be evaluated and cognitively constructed.

Furr, a personality psychologist, regarded the specificities of assessment psychology and proposed defining behaviour as "verbal utterances (excluding implicit feedback in psychological assessment scenarios) or movement patterns that are apparently available to meticulous observers using ordinary sensory processes" [Furr, 2009. p. 372]. Furr emphasised the "potentiality for behaviour to have direct social effects" by include perceptibility by others "through normal senses" in this definition [Furr, 2009. p. 372]. This criteria covers "possibly unintentional reactions" like trembling and look aversion, as well as bodily motions with "potentially significant social repercussions" [Furr, 2009. p. 372]. Other types of behaviour, including such verbal and nonverbal, purposeful and inadvertent, are relevant to this criteria. As a result, we may interpret behaviours through verbal statements. Furr emphasised the distinction between "unsolicited, spontaneous verbal assertions about one's (or another's) personality" and "verbal statements designed to respond to direct questioning by researchers in a personality assessment environment." "Verbal assertions about one's personality can definitely be deemed behaviours," according to this definition [Furr, 2009. p. 372].

Moreover, I.N. Gorelov defines a person's speech behaviour as "a complex of external and internal actions of a person who uses the national language. As a means of exchanging (with another person) the necessary information and expresses his attitude to a partner, to the information itself, to himself and conditions communication" [Gorelov, 2003. p. 14]. Most of Gorelov's works are devoted to the external, non-verbal actions of a person in communicating. In his psycholinguistic research "Non-verbal components of communication" [2007] he describes experimental data on the non-verbal components of communication in internal speech as found in texts and in the process of generating utterances. The author concludes that "the non-verbal components of communicative activity at the site of transmission of a message manifest themselves as rudiments of the oldest method of communication, which once again convinces us of the need to consider both synchronic and diachronic aspects of speech activity" [Gorelov, 2007.p. 104].

As a result, behaviour is an important mechanism for humans to externalise signals from their (completely internal) psychical processes to their surrounding environment. The above definitions demonstrate the variety of issues and meanings examined in many domains within the given concept. Furr's understanding of behaviour may be considered more thorough and applicable to our research.

Species-specific behaviours have developed to communicate crucial information in relatively consistent (presumably evolutionarily derived) and consequently constrained ways (Hinde, 1974). Individuals can communicate information in random and hence variable ways through external changes or actions other than species-specific behaviour (e.g., vocalisations, movements). The attribution of meanings functionalizes these externalisations, transforming them onto (semiotic) behaviours. When such assignments are made in socially shared ways by several persons, the specific behaviours become behavioural indicators (e.g., gestures, spoken language). Material events that are independent of persons' bodies (e.g., charcoal on stone) can likewise be ascribed meanings and therefore become material signals (e.g., drawings, texts). Human groups have created extensive behavioural and material marking systems (e.g., spoken, and written language). This approach “enables humans to overcome the fundamental imperceptibility of psychical phenomena by others and to communicate complex information that goes beyond that which can be externalised in species-specific behaviours (e.g.: communicative and noncommunicative)” [Uher, 2015, p. 216].

As a result, communicative behaviour may be viewed as a set of societal, age, gender, occupational, and individual conventions and traditions of people's communication. Halle [1989. p. 279 - 282] and I.A. Sternin [1989. p. 279—282] introduced the term "communicative conduct" in this meaning.

Sternin singled out the general cultural, group, situational, and individual norms of communicative behaviour [Sternin, 1989. p.279—282]. Universal cultural norms of communicative behaviour are inherent in all national cultures of the world. They reflect generally accepted rules of speech etiquette and cultural communication. These cultural norms of communicative behaviour may vary in

different situations. They do not depend on the gender of people, age, social status, type of professional activity, and others. An example of such norms is the day-to-day scenarios of greeting and farewell, contact, acquaintance, attracting attention, apology, talking on the phone, written message, congratulation, compliment, gratitude, wishes, consolation, sympathy, condolences.

Sternin paid great attention to models for a systematic description of communicative behaviour in his researches. He focused on people, a group, and an individual, based on contrastive research. He highlighted models [Sternin, 1989. p.279—282] that have options:

- for describing a national communicative behaviour,
- for describing group communicative behaviour,
- for describing personal communicative behaviour,
- giving options for describing national communicative behaviour
- giving options for describing group communicative behaviour.

Situational norms depend on the specific extralinguistic situation. Including restrictions on status, on the composition of communicating people, on the topic of communication. Situational conventions are nationally specific. For example, the interaction of the older generation with the younger in Muslim countries is much more vertical than in a European one. Communication between a man and a woman, under European norms, is horizontal from the status of communication perspective, while Muslim culture - vertical; and so on. Group norms reflect the specifics of communication characteristics of subcultures, professional cultures, and social groups. Individual guides of communicative behaviour reflect the distinct culture and communicative experience of an individual. And represent particular refraction of general cultural and situational communicative norms in a linguistic personality.

In addition, we can conditionally divide communicative behaviour into verbal and non-verbal. Verbal behaviour includes all behaviour that involves verbal means of communication within speaking, listening, writing, and reading. This interpretation is used by protagonists of a behavioristic understanding of language

(behaviourism). Here human verbal behaviour is explained by the set of motor and reducible to them verbal and emotional reactions of the body to stimuli of the external environment (direct or indirect). But it contrasts with the cognitive approach dominant in psycholinguistics and specifically with the theory of the cognitive task specificity of language [first described by B. F. Skinner, 1957].

In specific communication situations, verbal communicative behaviour is feasible according to the principles and norms of verbal communication. These are etiquette formulas, communication topics used in specific situations, a set and sequence of communication fragments used in various situations, the duration of communication in various circumstances, adherence to the specified timeframe for the deployment of the topic and these frames themselves in various situations, communication intervals of various groups of people.

Nonverbal communicative behaviour, on the other hand, is a collection of standards that control the criteria for nonverbal signals utilised in the communication process (gestures, postures, movement, facial expressions, gaze, physical contact, distance, choice of the place of communication, and others). "Nonverbal communication is an essential component of verbal communication in international communication because it adds meaning to verbal communication." [Sternin, 1989, p. 279-282].

E.A. Petrova stressed that while meeting in the first 12 seconds of communication, 92% of the information received by the interlocutors is non-verbal. In the first 20 minutes of communication, she claims, basic information about people's connections is mediated through interlocutors. As a result, nonverbal cues are endless. In his work "Body Language," A. Pease [Pease, 2004. p.386] According to statistics collected by A. Meyerbian, 7 percent of information was sent by verbal means (primarily words), 38 percent through sound means (such as tone of voice, intonation of sound), and 55 percent by non-verbal systems. Professor Birdwissl, in turn, reached to the very same conclusions, indicating that verbal communication accounts for less than 35 percent of a conversation and that more than 65 percent of information is transferred through nonverbal

communication. There is a functional distinction between verbal and nonverbal communication:

- we can communicate pure knowledge through the words channels,
- and we can verbally transmit our attitude toward the communication partner.

According to A. Pease [2004], the nonverbal channel contains around five times as much information as the verbal channel. Besides, the research made by Moskal & Egorov [2000] and Tufanova [2013] has justified the close relationships between verbal and non-verbal human behaviour in certain specific communicative conditions: in a situation of lying, apologizing, testifying, etc. Yu. V. Tufanova, at the heart of exploratory development, placed non-verbal means of representing the communicative behaviour of partners in a situation of apology. The results of her work allowed her to conclude that apology, accompanied by emotional stress. And the non-verbal behaviour of partners in apology is unity and interaction of facial expressions, gestures, and other non-verbal components of communication [Tufanova, 2013. p. 226].

As well as N. Yu. Katsnelenbogen draws attention to the similarity of verbal and non-verbal human behaviour in the sense that the basis of any utterance is limiting images; in written speech (as well as in oral), the evident desire to speak: like everybody, as is customary, as usual [Katsnelenbogen, 2008. p. 70], without which language cannot simply carry out functions in society.

The mentioned ideas in researches give evidence about the incorporation of verbal and non-verbal means of communication.

1.2. The main factors for organizing successful communication

The term "communication", which has Latin origin (*commūnicāre* - to share), means any kind of interaction in the broadest sense of the word. In a narrow sense, this term refers to the conscious and purposeful transfer of messages between individuals - participants in communication [Harder, 1999]. Since historical times, language, in a narrow definition, has been the main and only way of

communication. Verbal communication has long been considered the primary means of communicating a message.

Verbal (linguistic) communication is the most researched and universal type of human communication and is expressed in the exchange of thoughts, information, emotional experiences of the interlocutors [Sadokhin, 2009. p. 139-140].

Each culture creates its sign system, used by its carriers for communication purposes. Culture determines the linguistic picture of the world, which in turn, has a direct impact on the perception of the world by its representatives [Sadokhin, 2009.p. 140].

Verbal communication uses human speech as a sign system, natural sound language, i.e. the system of phonetic signs [Demushkina, 2015.p. 219]. Moreover, each word or sound has a specific meaning. With the help of speech, information is encoded and decoded: the speaker encodes in the process of speaking and the interlocutor decrypts the received reports [Alefirenko, 2009.p. 25-27].

In this scenario, it is reasonable to conclude that it makes absolutely no difference how significant people's beliefs, emotions, or connections are. Since communication is more about the conveyance of information than the transfer of emotional responses. Language is used to transmit information, thus it takes on a spoken form.

Furthermore, message exchange is not a "easy thing." To attain the communication aims, we must consider the personal meaning embedded in the speech. We don't simply deliver information throughout the communication process; we also inform, exchange expertise about the challenges of fixing an issue, and complain, and so on. That is to say, good communication is only feasible when the individual background of the sent message is considered. It's especially vital to remember this in verbal communication.

- What you say (and don't say),

- the words you use to communicate your views, the order in which you transfer messages to the addressee (where do you begin, how then do you progress, how do you stop),
- the arguments you make, whether you offer them succinctly or in depth, and many other factors.

It may appear to us that the manner in which we say something is less significant than the content of the message. Of course, the substance is critical, but the same material conveyed vocally by different persons and in diverse linguistic forms frequently produces an entirely different image - they will accept one but not the other. We fulfill someone's request, while another person's request is turned down. As a result, additional attention must be paid to the speech aspect of thinking expression.

Strong verbal speech influence requires appropriate (that is, proper, optimum, and effective in a particular scenario) use of communication norms and strategies, taking into consideration the interlocutors' backgrounds, communicative situations, the aim of communication, and other factors.

We may differentiate many groupings of elements among the norms and tactics of verbal speech impact. They are:

1. Communication norm compliance:

► Follow speech etiquette to guarantee that we preserve communicative balance, which is one of the most important prerequisites for speech impact efficacy. We can preserve regular connections with our interlocutor if we communicate respectfully and follow the acknowledged principles of communication etiquette. After all, we're demonstrating our admiration and our desire to stay up to them in future. All of this puts the interlocutor at our disposal, allowing us to exert effective control over him. Compliance with speaking etiquette norms is a significant weapon for persuading your audience. Nothing is as cheap or useful as civility, said the great Cervantes. Others believe that a person's etiquette in communications endows with a variety of positive characteristics.

► Observe the necessary cultural speech standards in order to construct the discourse in accordance with the cultural component. It is vital to appropriately emphasize. Also, use proper wording and refrain from using aggressive language. This type of discourse instills trust in its message. We may believe that this individual is well-educated. It might also indicate that one is intelligent and aware of the significance of the subject. Such a person's speech provides us with tremendously favorable knowledge about the speaker. We like and respect such individuals.

2. The potential to make connection with the interlocutor.

It is linked to the self-presentation mechanism: in order to communicate with the interlocutor, you must first predisposition the discussion participant. To create and sustain touch with the interlocutor, it is extremely important to follow the following conflict-free communication rules:

- talk less about yourself and more about the other person;
- enquire the interlocutor's difficulties;
- captivate the audience;
- compliment others;
- identify your own interests and those of the interlocutor;
- remember the happy moments you had throughout.
- individualize your conversation partner.

Naturally, we should communicate with the interlocutor in a courteous manner, adhering to societal standards.

3. Speech content factor.

The above criterion combines the principles that determine what is important to talk about and in what situations:

- discuss a topic that the interlocutor is interested in or should be interested in;
- more uplifting information should be communicated;
- negative information should be avoided;
- when you're not asked, do not give counsel (if assistance is still required, give it in the manner of caring);

- ▶ frequently refer to the opponent - the name rule;
- ▶ don't be baseless in your arguments;
- ▶ cite real-life examples;
- ▶ use ways to make the information your communication more credible.

4. The factor of language design.

This set of guidelines is related to the use of tangible language to express ideas:

- ▶ use synonyms that are similar in meaning to the term and phrase; diversify the words used;
- ▶ use words that inspire imagery rather than abstract ones; this involves using more descriptive terms (denoting activities, things) rather than abstract ones.
- ▶ use spoken language instead of textbook vocabulary;
- ▶ diversify your tone and avoid speaking in a monotonous manner.
- ▶ maintain the same speed as your companion (approximately -120 words a minute);
- ▶ round numbers while giving them out.

5. Factor of communication style.

The communicative style should demonstrate:

- ▶ friendliness, sincerity;
- ▶ inspiration;
- ▶ moderate emotionality;
- ▶ physical vigour, mobility.

6. The factor of the volume of the message.

Be brief. Use short, clear sentences.

7. The information's real place.

Give vital information at the start and by the finish of your speech, and then repeat it numerous times in various words throughout your speech.

8. The addressee.

It suggests thinking about the type of communicator or target. And to address them based on their distinct views, degrees of comprehension, and interests. You

must communicate with numerous people and convince them in various ways. "A speech should be tailored to the size of the listener, just as a garment should be tailored to the size of the buyer" [Sternin, 2012, p.51].

So there are several rules and convention revealed on the basis of described factors, which must be taking into consideration for effective organizing communication. Furthermore, throughout the transmission of information, verbal and nonverbal components of speech influence are inextricably linked. However, there is some imbalance in their roles at various stages of the communication act.

Nonverbal communication variables, according to some of the linguists, play the most important function at the period of individuals getting to know one another, the initial impression, and the categorization process (referring the collocutor to any category - , artful, rational, sincere and others). Non-verbal communication employs the same methods as verbal communication to communicate information between people, but it does so in a different way. Nonverbal communication can be used to support, enhance, or even replace speech ("clear without words" may be said in these cases). Nonverbal signals, on the other hand, serve the following purposes:

- ▶ delivering information towards the recipient
- ▶ affect the opponent;
- ▶ influence the speaker (self-action).

Nonverbal signs can be applied by the speaker intentionally or unconsciously in all of these roles. Nonverbal behaviour, on the other hand, is closely tied to his mental processes and acts as a method of expressing them. Nonlinguistic behavioural serves as an object of interpretation during conversation, not as a signal of a person's specific psychological and socio-psychological qualities that are hidden from direct observation. The psyche of the human is conveyed through nonverbal behaviour. It is carried out the construction of the content of communication and collaborative actions. People may swiftly alter their language patterns to changing situations, but their body is less adaptable.

Nonverbal communication encompasses about 700,000 facial and gesture motions of the hands and body, far more than words in our language. Furthermore, the greatest reflexive "keyboard" of non-speech "words" informs us person's genuine condition.

In modern scientific literature, the problems of non-verbal communication are widely discussed. One of the most outstanding works of recent years in this area can be called the work of G. Ye. Kreidlin "Non-verbal semiotics: body language and natural language" [Kreidlin, 2004]. The author reveals the ten special groups that make up non-verbal semiotics as Paralinguistics, Kinesics, Oculistics, Systemology the list goes on [Kreidlin, 2004. p. 22].

Nonverbal communication refers to human actions or attributes other than words. Following to this perspective, J. Burgoon & T. Saine define nonverbal communication as follows: "Nonverbal communication is all communication refers to actions which are sent out purposely, received with consciousness and may have a response". [Burgoon & Saine,1978. p.6-7].

At that time, non-verbal communication, being an element of the traditional behaviour of defined people, has a vivid national and temporary flavour, expresses situational realities. And therefore, the interest of linguists in this issue is easily explainable. Moreover, a misinterpretation in the translation of para-linguistic phenomena often leads to a distortion of the meaning of the translated text passage. The difficulty of such a translation lies in the ability to find a more concise form to explain a particular phenomenon.

James Borg emphasizes the relevance of the study of non-verbal communication, underlines that "Every day we are forced to constantly interpret what others tell us through their body language, as well as to control own body movements to make the desired impression on them. This is a two-way street! The overwhelming part of the information in the process of communication is subconsciously expressed in the form of a silent language, which either reinforces or refutes the spoken words" [Borg, 2013. p. 7-8].

So it is necessary to know the role, types and semiotic features of nonverbal means of communication.

1.3. Nonverbal means of communication

First, we need to give literature review of some researches to realize their types. The issues of national, gender and cultural specificity of non-verbal communication are raised in several studies. General aspects of national communicative consciousness are considered by I.A. Sternin [Sternin, 2002]. At the same time, Bagdasarova, exploring the universal and the national in the non-verbal behaviour of different cultures, faced a similar problem [Bagdasarova, 2006]. M. Moss's research deals with the functioning of non-verbal communication components in the rituals of Australians [Moss, 1996]. Smirnova studied non-verbal aspects of behaviour in Russian and English cultures [Smirnova, 1971], Galichev analysed some elements of proxemics and kinesics of speakers of German and Russian languages [Galichev, 1984]. The research of N. V. Dutova [2014, 2015] combines the national, gender, and cultural aspects while comparing Russian, English, and Chinese linguistic cultures. One of the most outstanding conclusions by N. V. Dutova is as follows: "Non-verbal communicative behaviour of a gender linguistic personality, regarding gender and linguistic culture of a particular gender type, reveals universal features" [Dutova, 2015. p. 93].

Works present by Vereshchagin [1981], Kostomarov [1981], Bogdanov, Katznelenbogen include information about non-verbal communication from the linguistic point of view, from the position of inclusion of non-verbal components in the expression of particular meaning in the process of communication.

E.M. Vereshchagin and V.G. Kostomarov characterize the units of non-verbal behaviour (gestures, facial expressions). They describe how facial gesture behaviour reflects in the forms of verbal language. The term they operate in the work is "kinesics", that is, "any finished (having a certain structure, method of performance and equally stable meaning) gesture movement" [Vereshchagin & Kostomarov, 1981 p. 37]. The work describes noted mass kinemes, demonstrating

the national-cultural specifics of facial expressions and gestures. As well as general linguistic ways of expressing based on the unity, in fixing the kinema, with the corresponding utterances [Vereshchagin & Kostomarov, 1981 p. 47].

These works contributed the development of theoretical assumptions, functions, classifications and cultural specificity of nonverbal means of communication. Let's move to dealing with the matters of different types of non-verbal means and their semiotics.

A study of the literature demonstrates that nonverbal messages, the same as words, are polysemantic. Depending on the context, a nonverbal "head nod" might mean a range of things, including agreement, attention, appreciation, incentive, thanks, recognition, welcoming, permitting, and so on.

According to E.A.Petrova's research, gestures during official communication approach national and cultural standards. Individuality emerges via conversational dialogue. Nonverbal communication is more visible and used by children and youths, and it gradually declines as a native speaker ages.

Various categories of nonverbal modes of communication have been proposed in socio-psychological studies. They encompass all body motions, voice intonation features, tactile impacts, and communication spatial structure (see **Appendix 1**).

Kinetics is one of the most important nonverbal means. These are another person's visually perceived motions that have an expressive-regulatory role in communication. Kinesics includes expressive movements such as facial expressions, posture, position, gaze, and stride.

Facial expressions - spontaneous movements of the facial muscles, which are not without reason referred to as the mirrors of the soul - play a key role in the transfer of information. According to studies, when a lecturer's face remains unmoving or unseen, up to 10-15 per cent of content may be lost.

The essential feature of facial movements is their integrity and dynamism. Mimics indicate six basic emotional responses (anger, joy, fear, suffering, surprise, and disgust), and all motions of the muscles of the face are synchronised, as

demonstrated by V.A. Labunskaya's [1999] system of mimic coding of emotional states. (see **Appendix 1**)

According to studies, notwithstanding ethnicity or culture of origin, all individuals perceive these mimicking structures as a representation of the relevant emotions with adequate accuracy and consistency. And, whereas each mimic code is a different mask of the face. However, the brows and the region surrounding the mouth (lips) convey more information. Thus, the individuals were shown pictures of faces with only the location of the brows and mouth changing. The individuals' ratings were remarkably consistent - emotion recognition was nearly 100%. Joy, surprise, contempt, and rage are the most immediately identified emotions. While despair and dread, are harder recognised.

One of the most efficient and effective friendly facial expressions, the foundation of which, is a smiling face. A smile has many functions in communication: it characterises a cheerful human as a holder of good signs, as a nice person; it elicits positivity in the interlocutor, which easily mirrors; it brightens up the narrator; it encourages the progression of contact; it trains about forty facial muscles, prevents future wrinkles, and it reduces pain.

The movement of the brows during a smile indicates sincerity, but if the brows remain stationary and the individual grins only with his lips, the smile is false.

The look, or eye contact, that is a communication landmark, is strongly tied to facial emotions. People seek reciprocity while speaking and are uncomfortable when facial emotions are lacking. The eagerness to communicate is shown through eye contact. We may argue that if someone looks at us too long, this is a warning to us or positive attitude toward us but if opponent focuses on us just a little, we do have the reason to suppose that people treat us or even what we say and do negatively. The most precise indications regarding a person's state are sent through the eyes. Since pupil expansion and contraction cannot be deliberately controlled. The pupils dilate or constrict depending on the situation when exposed to a steady light. When a person is eager, interested, or in a good mood, pupils dilate four

times more than they normally do. A furious, gloomy attitude, on the other hand, causes the pupils to constrict.

Maintaining contact is defined as focusing at the addressee for at least half of the discourse. An amicable, smiling expression, in eyecontact is interpreted as indicating a pleasant attitude, attention, compassion, and a desire for interaction. Following the discourse as well may be interpreted in smiling, nodding at the interlocutor 60–70% of the time.

When communicating over an extended period of time, etiquette dictates that you glance at your interlocutor's face rather than his or her eyes. Looking someone in the eyes is considered hostile. When dealing with business concerns, employ a business look focused towards the "eye-nose" triangle to convey the honesty of intentions. In friendly chat, lower the glance - to that of the "eye-mouth" triangular, such a stare displays a welcoming attitude, and a desire to interact. The gaze downwards, from the head to the breast, is referred to as intimate, and it expresses personal attention. A sidelong gaze frequently conveys either curiosity or anger. Whenever anyone interacts with slightly lifted brows or a grin, they are expressing curiosity. If it is associated with drooping brows, frowning brows, or drooping corners of the lips, it implies a suspicious or sardonic attitude. If the speaker is hostile to you or attempts to put you under pressure, gaze into his "third eye," which is located just a bridge of the nose. This may increase your communicative stance while weakening the position of an interlocutor.

Thus, not only a person's face in general but exactly gaze, convey a huge range of information. On the other hand, facial expressions are more carefully controlled than physical motions. Considering this fact body is more revealing in many instances. When a person, for example, wishes to hide his feelings or purposely give misleading data, words become misinforming, and the body is becoming the primary resource of information for the person.

The posture is the orientation of the human body that is characteristic of a certain culture, and it is an essential unit of spatial individual behaviour. The human body is capable of around 1000 different stable postures. Some jobs are

restricted owing to the cultural traditions of each nation, while others are established. The position clearly demonstrates how a specific person feels his own status in relation to the status of those present. Higher-status individuals adopt more comfortable body posture than their subordinates.

A. Scheflen [1967] was among the first to recognize human posture as a nonverbal mode of communication. Further research by V. Schubts [1978] demonstrated that the major semantic value of the stance consisted of the individual's bodily location with the interlocutor. This location suggests either proximity or a desire to communicate.

It has been demonstrated that the "locked" pose (when a person attempts to close the whole front part of the body and take up the as little area as possible; "Napoleonic" pose, standing: arms managed to cross just on the abdomen, as well as sitting: two hands rest on the cheekbone, and so on.) are viewed as positions of deep mistrust, disagreement, opposition, and criticism. Postures of confidence, agreement, compassion, and psychological comfort are presented as standing with arms spread, palms up; sitting with outstretched arms, legs extended.

A person who wants to "put himself" will stand up straight, tight, with unfolded shoulders, occasionally holding his arm on the hips; a person who does not need to underline his status and position will be comfortable, peaceful, and in a free, relaxed stance. There are also read meditation postures (the attitude of Rodin's thinker) and postures of critical examination (when the hand is under the chin, index finger extended to the temple). If a person is engaged in conversation, he concentrates on the interlocutor and leans in his direction; if he is not interested, he will reorient himself to the side and lean slightly.

Almost everyone knows how to "read" positions, albeit they don't necessarily know how they do so. The meanings of gestures, those varied movements of the head and hands whose meaning is evident to the sender and recipient, may be comprehended as simply as posture. Much is discovered about the signals that gestures provide. First and foremost, the number of motions is significant. Regardless of how varied cultures are, worldwide, along with the increase in

emotional experiences, the frequency of gesticulation develops and also when you want to obtain a comprehensive understanding between participants, particularly if it is somehow hard.

It is well known that the particular significance of certain gestures varies by culture. However, all cultures have similar gestures, which include:

- modal gestures (gestures of approval and dissatisfaction, trust and distrust, confusion);
- descriptive gesticulations that make sense only in the context of a speech utterance;
- and communicative gestures (gestures of greeting, goodbye, prohibitions, attracting attention, negative, satisfactory, negative, interrogative).

The concurrence of gestures and voice utterances, or congruence, should not be overlooked during communication. A discrepancy between gestures and the meaning of utterances is an indication of deception. Speech statements and accompanying gestures must be consistent.

Finally, a person's stride, or moving pattern, may clearly reveal their emotional condition, it was discovered that the heavy walk is associated with hatred, the lightest with joy, the slow, depressing gait is associated with suffering, and the longest stride is associated with pride. Thus, in lingua-psychological investigations, individuals with pinpoint precision judged by gait key emotions as wrath, sorrow, pride, and enjoyment.

The link between gait and personal traits appears to be more intricate. The judgments regarding what a walk may represent are based on a comparison of physical and personal attributes determined through testing.

We can also correlate voice with a variety of nonverbal modes of communication. Prosodic and extralinguistic phenomena are the two types of voice characteristics.

Prosody is the umbrella term for the rhythmic and intonational characteristics of speech such as pitch, tone, timbre, and stress strength. Speech pauses and a

range of psychophysiological symptoms of a person, such as sobbing, coughing, laughing, sighing, and many others, are all part of the extralinguistic system. Prosodic and extra-linguistic methods of communication are used to regulate the flow of speech, conserve linguistic means of communication, augment, substitute, and predict spoken utterances, and communicate emotional states. Grief, grief, and exhaustion are typically expressed in a quiet, muffled voice, with a reduction in intonation at the conclusion of the phrase. While enthusiasm, delight, and distrust are typically expressed in a high-pitched voice, similar to wrath and fear, but with a broader range of timbre, power, and pitch of sounds.

Speech tempo also reflects emotions: slow speech might be indicative of despair, sorrow, hubris, or exhaustion while rapid speech indicates enthusiasm or anxiety. It appears to be instructive to detect what movement is produced when pronouncing a certain phrase by voice, and vice versa, by monitoring gestures throughout the speech, we may understand what voice the person is speaking in. You must be able to hear not only the intonation structure of speech, but also the strength and tone of voice, as well as the speed of speech, all of which enable us to convey our feelings, thoughts, and volitional aspirations not only alongside, but also in addition to, and sometimes despite, the word. As a result, we must remember that our gestures and words might occasionally contradict what we say. So all these processes must be controlled and synchronised.

Dynamic contact in a handshake, patting, and kiss are examples of tactile communication. The use of touch in interaction can be influenced by a variety of things. Among these are relationship status, age, gender, and degree of familiarity. Touch has been proved to be a biologically required kind of stimulation, rather than merely a minor aspect of human communication.

Handshakes, for example, are classified as dominating (hand on top, palm down), submissive (palm up, hand below), and equal. A pat on the back is possible if the communicants have close ties and are of equal social rank.

The tactical methods of communication, more than other nonverbal means, give an indication of status-role relations and a representation of the communicators'

degree of closeness. Improper usage of them by an individual might result in communication difficulties.

Furthermore, communication is always arranged geographically. An American anthropologist E. Hall was among the first to investigate the geographical structure of communication, coining the word "proxemics," which literally means "proximity." The direction of partners during conversation, as well as the distance between them, are examples of proxemic traits. Cultural and national variables may have a direct impact on proxemic indices. E. Hall highlighted the approaching norms - the gaps that are distinctive of North American culture:

- ▶ Intimate distance (from 0cm to 45 cm) - interaction between close friends;
- ▶ Personal (45cm to 120 cm) - contact with known persons;
- ▶ Social (120cm to 400 cm) - interacting with outsiders and during formal conversation;
- ▶ Public (400cm to 750 cm) - speaking in front of a variety of audiences.

Violation of the ideal communication distance is seen negatively. The nonverbal system's proxemic components are orientation and communication angle. Orientation, indicated in physical turn and toes towards or away from the partner, in particular, indicates the direction of thinking. The locations of the communicative parties at the table are determined by the nature of the conversation.

Figure 1: The positions of the communicating parties at the table.

People sit opposite while communicating in a competitive or defensive manner; in an ordinary amicable chat, adopt a corner position; in cooperative behaviour,

arrange business interactions on one side of the desk; and in an independent stance, take a diagonal posture.

As previously stated, nonverbal behaviour serves several purposes:

- ▶ it conjures up a mental image of a communicator;
- ▶ expresses and establishes the interaction of communicants;
- ▶ is a reflection of the individual's current mental state;
- ▶ functions as a clarification, alters interpretation of the spoken content, and increases the emotive depth of what was stated;
- ▶ maintains a high level of psychological connection among communicators;
- ▶ functions as a predictor of status-role correlations.

Nonverbal ways of strengthening enable the narrator to intensify communicative stance, hence increasing communication efficacy. Among these nonverbal messages, various factors that integrate the same type of signal, including appearance factor, may be distinguished:

- *Clothes*. Dark traditional attire, substantial substance, and the juxtaposition of dark and white tones improve the communication posture. High hats, heels, and dark horn-rimmed glasses complete the look. Clean, tidy clothing appears favourable. The bright colours of the garments signify that the wearer is happy and successful. The cautious pursuit of fashion trends boosts the speaker's communication posture.

- *The hairstyle*. A high hairdo elevates the wearer's status. Interestingly, blondes are viewed as more appealing, but also superficial and shallow in their judgements, whilst brunettes are recognized as more serious, intellectual, and competent. A man's short hairdo may convey efficiency and poor intelligence, whereas long hair conveys creativity and intellectuality.

- *The silhouette*. The closer the shadow figure is to a rectangle, the stronger the impression we can make. A person's position is strengthened by wearing apparel with a rectangular shape (and, conversely, a spherical silhouette, raglan sleeve, soft sweaters, and jeans weaken the communicative position of the speaker). A typical

English suit (with shoulder pads) for a lady and a suit for a male might provide the impression of an authoritative, professional, and dependable individual.

- *Adding*. The communicative posture is enhanced by his tall size and athletic frame. Tall folks have a lot of power.

- *Physical attractiveness* is linked to excellent human characteristics. Many people associate physically attractive people with being socially adept, persuasive (able to persuade), popular, successful, happy, and having a large number of friends.

Outcomes of the first chapter

Verbal and nonverbal behaviour and its components are objects of deep research in different sciences. Researches of different aspects of the process of communication are of great importance and make the topicality of our analysis. In the first chapter, we tried to analyze the processes of verbal and nonverbal behaviour. Communicative behaviour is defined by scholars as behaviour (verbal and accompanying non-verbal) of a linguocultural community (people, social group) or a person in the process of communication, regulated by the norms and traditions of communication of a given society. That has the following peculiar characteristics: "norms" and "models" of communicative behaviour.

Every individual has a distinct communication style via which they communicate and exchange ideas with others. As a result, people from different cultures have diverse nonverbal styles and utilise different nonverbal techniques to communicate themselves. And what is a standard for one culture might be understood differently by representatives of another culture's cultural frame.

Members of distinct cultures perceive the environment in personally identifiable patterns, and when certain nonverbal cues, postures, or movements are not understood, these gestures, stances, or movements constitute clear communication hurdles. As a result, in all circumstances of cross-cultural dialogue, we must be extremely cautious, courteous, and thoughtful.

To sum up, I can say that the differences in communication among different cultures, we first need to Semantic peculiarities of nonverbal means of

communication and define pragmatic difficulties in the application of nonverbal means.

CHAPTER II. SEMANTIC PECULIARITIES OF NONVERBAL MEANS OF COMMUNICATION

2.1. Approaches to discovering semantic features of nonverbal means of communication

Non-verbal communication plays an important role in the process of communication, being a means of meaning transfer. The theoretical approach to non-verbal communications, non-verbal behaviour as a direct expression in the communication of the semantic sphere, and the semantic position of the individual is developed in the study of V. I. Ekintsev [2011]. According to the author, the assessment of the severity of the semantic position is expressed precisely in gestures, which is considered a condition for internal dialogue in the mechanism for solving the problem of meaning. When completing heuristic, visual tasks, a person addresses a gesture as a way of conveying a semantic position to himself as a subject of action, serving as a reflective means that maintains the meaning at the time of its transfer from an irrational to a rational (verbal) form. In other words, non-verbalized meanings-signs (gestures) become verbalised.

Surkamp C. endows non-verbal behaviour with a compensatory function, for example, non-verbal communication can help in learning, for example, a foreign language, since the lack of vocabulary or the inability to reproduce speech can be compensated by decoding speech signals or transferring part of the communicative intention to the modality of gesture [Stuttgart, 2018. p 17]. In other words, non-verbal communication can understand the meaning and meaning of information, but also help the learner to express their thoughts and feelings. Thus, the emotional function of non-verbal behaviour provides valuable information about the emotions and intentions of their interlocutor in language emergencies.

Strunina E.N. [2013. p.14] determines the gender specificity of nonverbal communication, giving women the ability to better read their partner's body language, conditioned by the fact that they had experience in raising children at the preverbal level. For example, in the Western business world, it is women who are more often sent to negotiations. Indeed, cultural differences are especially crucial

to consider during commercial talks. Experienced communicators and negotiators, for example, can accurately read information while maintaining eye contact. In commercial meetings, Middle Eastern officials frequently wear dark glasses to avoid revealing their genuine feelings and sentiments through nonverbal signs. As a result, the conditionality of the individual's culture, his affiliation to the people, influences nonverbal communication (nation).

N. Yu. Katsnelbogen [2008] in the framework of both verbal and non-verbal behaviour, the author identifies three levels of manifestation and formation of national culture:

- 1) basic stereotyped core of knowledge;
- 2) peripheral stereotyped knowledge;
- 3) the personal level [Katsnelbogen, 2008. p. 70].

But this does not mean that every native speaker has the same set of stereotypes of communicative behaviour (idio-reflexes or phrase-reflexes).

Researcher D.A. Abduazizova examined the paralinguistic means used in the verbal and non-verbal speech of the English, Americans, Russians, and Uzbeks [Abduazizova, 1997]. In her research, the scholar compared translations of works to find out how adequate the transmission of paralinguistic means is. She concluded that in a comparative typological study of paralinguistic means, three types of paralinguistic interference occur:

- paraphonetic (when the phonation skills of native speakers are subject to transfer when studying a foreign language),
- parakinetic (when gestures, facial expressions, and body movements are transferred to a foreign)
- and paragraph (when there are significant differences in the execution of letters and symbols, etc.).

The interaction of language and culture, and language stereotypes of different cultures are reflected in the theories of intercultural communication. The development of these theories in the second half of the 20th century is associated

with progress in the field of science and technology, the improvement of information technology and the exchange of knowledge on a global scale.

A.M. Zheleznyak expresses the opinion that English speakers should be easier for a person with a phlegmatic temperament - calm, restrained, unhurried [Zheleznyak, 2005. p 17]. It seems to us that this thesis, based on the analytical structure of the English language, overgeneralizes the nature of English speakers and does not take into account other extralinguistic factors.

The set of non-verbal elements used in the process of communication corresponds to the cultural attitudes of individuals and depends on factors of an extralinguistic nature. Each culture has its own set of rules that determine the set of non-verbal means. Communicators not only actively use the established rules but also interpret the behaviour of their interlocutors based on their own attitudes [Matsumoto, 2003]. A similar opinion is expressed by A.P. Sadokhin [2004. p 152], speaking about culturally conditioned gestures that are symbols and have a contractual character depending on cultural origin.

Americans, accustomed to direct, non-mediated verbal expression of thought, do not always understand the subtle nuances of the non-verbal language of representatives of other cultures. Americans pay special attention to non-verbal paralinguistic elements - pauses and their fillers. "The American, rational in his outlook on life and accustomed to tact, usually makes many small intermissions during a conversation" [Wisson, 2005. p 137].

At the same time, as mentioned above, there are elements of non-verbal communication that are physiological in nature. All people, regardless of nationality, culture, sociolinguistic attitudes - communication situation, age, gender, social status - express universal emotions (anger, contempt, disgust, fear, joy, sadness and surprise) in almost the same ways. These facial expressions, which always carry the same meaning, have been observed in humans all over the world and have also been recorded in primates and people who are blind from birth. There are types of non-verbal behaviour common to many cultures -

greeting, farewell, etc. [Matsumoto, 2003]. Thus, the basic human emotions are often physiological, and therefore universal for all mankind.

For most Russians in the 18th and 19th centuries, morality was inextricably linked with Orthodoxy - this is religious morality. However, Russian people have always respected the labour morality upon which the ideology was established. The Russian guy is the most upright, religious, impoverished, hardworking, and unmercenary. Puritans ruled and dominated in the United States, with their rigorous and fundamental labour morality. The American is the most righteous, the most productive, and hence the richest. As we can see, there are both similarities and contrasts in Russia. In Russia, vast riches has traditionally been regarded with suspicion ("You cannot build stone rooms from the labours of the righteous"). In the United States, wealth has always been considered an honorary lot of the most pious.

2.2. Cross-cultural analysis of nonverbal means of communication

First of all, it is necessary to define the concept of "culture", which has several meanings depending on the context of its use. Until the end of the 18th century, culture was often associated with the concept of "civilization". In the 19th century, with the Enlightenment, comes the concept of culture as the intellectual development of the individual, the ability of the individual to properly behave in society. Culture is associated with the development of the state and society as a whole - the level of development of industry, democracy, class division and art. E.B. Tyler defines culture as the totality of knowledge, beliefs, traditions and customs necessary for the individual as a member of society [Tyler, 1891]. In the past, culture was seen as "a map of behaviour", while now culture is mostly defined as "a map for behaviour" [Sarangi, 2001]. It turns out that in the past, culture was considered a reflection of the behaviour of individuals. At present, it is widely believed that culture itself is a defining part of the behaviour of the

individual. Often the concept of culture is associated with a particular nation or state.

The interaction of culture and language can be traced back to the works of W. Humboldt, who explicitly states that culture is embodied in language and has a national character, which is expressed in a special vision of the world [Humboldt, 1985, p 247]. The relationship between language and culture was supported in the works of I.A. Baudouin de Courtenay, L. Elmslev, A.A. Potebnya, R.O. Jakobson [Baudouin de Courtenay, 1963. Elmslev, 2006. Potebnya, 2000. Jakobson, 1985]. The definition of culture as a fundamental part of an individual's behaviour is called cultural determinism [Sarangi, 2001]. The hypothesis of linguistic relativity by E. Sapir and B. Whorf supports linguistic determinism. According to it, the world is presented to people through the prism of their native language, which forms their thoughts and feelings. Language determines the perception of reality and influences the cultural differences between speakers of different languages [Sapir, 1949. Whorf, 1956.]. Most linguists are of the opinion about the relative determinism of culture over language. This position assumes the relationship and interdependence of language and culture.

The study of the role of culture in the process of communication is associated with the anthropocentric paradigm and the analysis of "man in language" and "language in man". At the end of the 20th century, linguoculturology develops, and language begins to be considered a product of culture, a factor in the formation of cultural codes, i.e. the subject of linguoculturology is language and culture, which are in dialogue and interaction [Maslova, 2001. p.6-8]. This paradigm follows the relationship between culture and language. On the one hand, language is the consequence of people's activities, and on the other, it is a factor shaping the linguistic image of the carriers of a certain culture.

Some people believe that cultural differences are caused by communication difficulties. E. Hall, the pioneer of intercultural communication theory, conveys the notion of communication and culture's homogeneity and intrinsic determinism. C

He believes, that “culture, is communication, and communication is culture” [Hall, 1959, p.137].

Culture has an impact on the linguistic picture of the world that has developed in the mind of the bearer of this culture. The linguistic picture of the world precedes and forms other pictures of the world. “Features of the language determine how a person sees himself and the world around him” [Maslova, 2001. p.64-65]. Cultural affiliation plays the role of a significant factor in the speech and non-verbal behaviour of interlocutors. It determines the mentality of communicants, which directly affects their choice of linguistic and non-linguistic means, influences the speech behaviour of each individual - the way to present one's speech, build arguments, and have their “own system of speech etiquette and politeness” [Hinnenkamp, 1995]. Already ancient thinkers (Herodotus, Thucydides) noted the fact that each people has its own characteristics that distinguish it from other peoples. The concept of mentality can be considered in a broad and narrow sense. In the narrow sense of the word, “mentality is what allows one to perceive the surrounding reality in a uniform way, evaluate it and act in it in accordance with certain norms and patterns of behaviour established in society, adequately perceiving and understanding each other.”

In the broad sense of the word, “mentality is a set of symbols that are formed within the framework of each given historical and cultural era and nationality. This set of symbols is fixed in the minds of people in the process of communicating with their own kind, that is, by repetition. These symbols (concepts, images, ideas) serve in everyday life as an explanation, a way of expressing knowledge about the world and the person in it” [Shcheglova, 2002. p.59-60]. Thanks to the study of the language, it becomes possible to highlight the mentality of its speakers and determine their cultural characteristics.

Analyzing the function of culture in language, it is necessary to note the role of culture in the formation of not only the linguistic picture of the world and the mentality of speakers, but also in the “formation of cultural stereotypes that are factors in behaviour, the individual unconscious and consciousness” [Maslova,

2001, p.64]. Each nationality has its own stereotypes of behaviour that are on the conscious and unconscious level of the linguistic personality.

Cross-cultural communication is a form of communication which aims to share information across different cultures and social groups. With the development of the globalization, communication among different countries has become very common particularly in the business field. There is no denying that the knowledge of different cultures plays a highly important role in the intercultural communication.

"There is language in her eye, her cheek, her lip," William Shakespeare famously said about nonverbal communication. "No, her foot talks." In the 1950s, American psychologist Albert Mehrabian, a pioneer in body language research, discovered that "the entire effect of a communication is around 7% verbal (words alone), 38% vocal (including tone of voice, inflection, and other sounds), and 55% nonverbal" [Mehrabian, 2007]. As a result, the significance of nonverbal behavior is obvious.

Nonverbal communication is not just the body language, but also something related transmitting information. Larry A. Samovar [2004] ever defined nonverbal communication as all these nonverbal stimuli in a communication setting that are generated by both the source and his/her use of the environment and that have potential message value for the source or receiver. To put it simply, the messages that can be transmitted are intentional and unintentional behaviors, which have a wide range, such as facial expression, eye contact, gestures, postures, space and distance. In order to get a full understanding and avoid some unnecessary misunderstandings of nonverbal meanings from the opposite side, we should bear in mind various factors, especially culture differences.

Nonverbal communication is deeply rooted in culture. Culture values and norms make an influence on nonverbal communication and determine what kind of nonverbal behavior is appropriate. On the other hand, nonverbal communication is a mirror reflecting different cultures. In this paper the author will use comparative method to discuss several nonverbal factors quite often used in daily life, which

may cause misunderstanding and awkward to Westerners and Chinese in cross-cultural communication.

1. FACIAL EXPRESSIONS

Feeling happy, all over the world we smile, while the emotions of enjoyment, sadness, fear, anger and surprise are just presupposed to be expressed similarly: the frequency and context of using these facial expressions vary from culture to culture.

Expressing a negative attitude toward something in the presence of others is uncharacteristic for Americans, which is the reason for the frequent use of a smile in the process of communication. National American tradition says no matter what happens, you need to smile (keep smiling). This phenomenon is called the "American smile code" [Wierzbicka, 1999]. According to the "code" described above, representatives of American culture do not show their bad mood and their problems to other people. They do not see the point in this and consider it wrong concerning their interlocutors.

It is customary for Americans to smile when looking at children or animals. 90% of Americans smile while greeting.

Russian culture, by L. Visson's point, is rather characterized by a pessimistic attitude associated with the psychologically difficult history of Russia. "If a Russian smiles, this, as a rule, is a manifestation of sincerity and a good mood." [Visson 2005, p. 115-116].

Americans typically smile with their "teeth." They display both their top and bottom teeth when they smile. M. Gorky, a Russian writer who toured America in the 1930s, wrote, "The first thing you perceive on an American's face is teeth." Russians grin more subtly, with "lips" that expose just the bottom set of teeth. In execution, the American smile recalls the Russian grin, that is, the showing of teeth by animals, and is viewed with caution, often disapprovingly, as unnatural, showy, and dishonest.

2. EYE CONTACT

In interpersonal communication, it's indispensable to stay in eye contact with others. In fact, in several nations and cultures, the utilization of eye contact is sort of different. Sometimes, they have opposite meanings. Within the communication among Western countries, taking America and England for instance, straight eye contact may be a sign showing upright and honesty. A proverb in Western countries goes, "Never trust people who can't look in your eyes." Without straight eye contact, the person is going to be considered timid, not confident and impolite. In England and France, gentlemen stare at the feminine to point out appreciation, which may be a publicly recognized cultural value. According to a scientific study, "the typical duration of eye contact is 2.95 seconds, and therefore the average duration of the time two people look at one another is 1.18 seconds" [Argyle, 1994]. On the contrary, in Russian communication, this system causes hostility towards the beholder.

These differences can cause miscommunication within multicultural communication. Being conscious of different cultures and showing respect, and understanding of the various implications of eye contact in several cultural contexts is friendly to others and also as beneficial to one's part.

3. SILENCE

Even in a large corporation, you can be silent for a short period of time, according to American communication conventions. That will not compel others to force you to speak with the interlocutor. Furthermore, it will not draw any notice to you. "Embarrassing quiet" has no meaning in America. At the table, the discussion should not be carried on by everyone at the same time and in the same way.

Most Americans hate silence and find silence uncomfortable, trying to fill every gap in the conversation. This is why "free-talk" is an integral part of most conversations.

The topics of such conversations can be the weather, movies, books, family or social events. The traditional greeting may be followed by a phrase like "The weather is wonderful, isn't it?". Then the conversation continues on any of the above topics. Such conversations can be heard everywhere.

Americans are characterized by a love for the sound accompaniment of activities. Very often, students and schoolchildren study to the accompaniment of the player, and housewives use as a companion TV to fill the “audio gap”. When driving to work, almost all Americans turn on the radio.

For Russians who have come to the States and adhere to the principle “silence is golden”, this state of affairs can cause some discomfort [Lanier, 2017. p15-16.]

4. GESTURES

Gestures are the movement of fingers to speak with one another and express ideas. They can often take the place of verbal language to start and stop communication, sometimes explaining and strengthening what people express. Some researchers from Levy Bruhl, Lucien [2010] showed that at the initial time, while tribes of India had different verbal languages, they might communicate and understand one another through gestures. In modern society, the gesture remains an efficient and irreplaceable way of communication. In cross-culture communication, people with language barriers more often use gestures to precise something. The utilization of gestures is flexible and filled with various meanings, particularly in a different culture.

For Russians, a raised thumb symbolizes the highest rating. In the USA, this gesture may mean - everything goes well or - the desire to catch a passing car, and if the finger is sharply thrown up, this is an obscene expression. How the finger is thrown (at least until recently) did not matter in Russian culture, but in America, this detail radically modifies what was said.

Even minor changes in a gesture can radically alter its meaning. So it happened in England with two fingers, index and middle, raised. If the palm is turned towards the interlocutor at the same moment, this is a horrible insult. When the palm is turned towards oneself, the initial letter of the word "victory" appears (victory). We've seen how well-known politicians have used this gesture to convey their excitement, and we've also seen a forest of "Vs" rise up over the heads of their followers who greeted them.

Also, the classic Russian gesture indicating "I'm tired of this" (running the edge of the palm down the neck) is never employed in this context in the United States.

Some gestures in Russian and American cultures may be similar. Counting is done using fingers, however the Russians bend them, beginning with the pinkie. And the Americans unbend them with the thumb, or count by tapping the index finger of one hand to the fingertips of the open palm of the other hand alternately. A handshake is a symbol of greeting in both nations, although in the United States, it is generally brief and strong, with arms extended fully. In Russia, the arms are bent, and the longer the handshake, the greater respect.

Calling with a flexible index finger is permitted in the United States but not acceptable in Russia. It is considered impolite among Russians to point toward something at a close distance with the forefinger. Because this gesture is deemed overly dictatorial and powerful, if it is required, for instance, to point out a word to a pupil in a book open in front of him, the instructor consistently showed the middle finger, which appears impolite to Americans. In the United States, whistling and stomping your feet during a performance or other social event is regarded as a show of approval.

The conclusion is obvious: if the exact meanings of gestures are unknown, it is better to exclude them altogether when communicating with foreigners. These gestures are either not understood or have a different interpretation.

5. POSTURES

Postures refer to transmitting messages through body movement. While communicating, postures could tell us about social station, religion, desire and intention. The recognition of one posture in comparison with another and the emotion conveyed by a given posture seems to be largely determined by culture [Samovar, 2004. p.168]. During a communication, we may unconsciously put our soles to others while sticking one leg over the opposite. It may be considered as disrespect for Russians, whereas among Americans it's simply how to point out feeling relaxed.

Another posture Americans usually use is shrugging shoulders. It can be interpreted that they are innocent and have no secret to conceal. But in Russia, it can be expressed as indifference and ignorance.

Smartness and proper posture are extremely important to Americans. It, like a grin, is meant to communicate good health (which is critical) and the absence of issues. Americans attempt to appear athletic and lively. Americans' elderly are brighter and better-dressed than Russians. Americans, more than Russians, have an upright posture when sitting, and they do not stoop as much when eating as Russians.

Americans can sit in transport and office with their ankle on the knee of the other leg (the “four” position), this position is considered acceptable. You can put your feet on the table in certain situations.

In Russia, putting your feet on furniture is indecent. The Americans, on the other hand, do not see anything indecent in this. Therefore, they calmly settle down even at official events in a way that suits them. They do this not because they want to offend us with something, but because it is acceptable in their country.

6. SPACE AND DISTANCE

In 1963, Edward T. Hall [1976] referred to the concept of “proxemics” which generalizes the researches on interpersonal distance. Through study, he divided interpersonal distance of American into four part, namely intimate distance(0~45cm), personal distance(46~122cm), social distance(122~366cm) and public distance(366~750cm). At dealing with official business, people mostly keep the social distance with each other.

Everyone has a certain interpersonal distance where it makes people feel comfortable in communication. There also exists a connection between culture and preferred interpersonal distance. During a communication, the Spanish and the Arabian can get closer and closer; but to the English, it is too close in communicating with the Italian. Communication among the Latin American of the same sex is almost next to skin. At the end of the communication of between the

Arabian and the American, they could stand at a place far away from the original place, for the former ones are prone to move forward showing friendliness while the latter ones are used to moving backward avoiding closer distance. In fact, people of different cultures are just looking for an appropriate and accustomed distance in communication.

What's more, people in Western culture pay more attention to privacy than those in Eastern culture and they show great respect to personal space. For instance, Chinese people have higher tolerance to the crowded place than the Westerns, such as in elevator and bus. No matter it is for general or business conversation, if you want people feel comfortable with you, the golden rule is "keep our distance".

7. PHISICAL CONTACT

Americans is not a connect culture. When it comes to personal touch, Americans are highly reticent. Such encounters are relatively rare: the rule Keeping your hands to yourself is effective. Only males are permitted to greet each other by patting each other on the shoulder. A. Leinier, on the other hand, observes that, while Americans require a somewhat big "comfort zone" while speaking, they frequently communicate by touch. They can, for example, put a hand on the interlocutor's shoulder to express their friendliness or even hug him as a symbol of their sympathy, lightly nudge him under the ribs while telling some funny story, pat him on the back in consolation and stroke the child on the head to express their love, and often hug each other tightly when greeting and parting. "They will gladly grasp the interlocutor's hand and assist them in crossing the street." [Lanier, pages 17-18]

8. HANDSHAKE

The American handshake is odd, and it is difficult for a foreigner to grasp when it is appropriate to shake hands with an American and when it is preferable not to. When two individuals meet in a regular circumstance, it is typical for them to shake hands, but this is not obligatory. Even close friends in America seldom shake hands unless they haven't seen one other in a long time or wish to

congratulate each other. At the initial meeting and departure, a handshake is possible. In a dating environment, greetings are frequently followed with a smile, handshake and eye contact. Americans normally just shake hands for just few seconds. They have a firm handshake; others who do not shake hands hard enough comment, "He shakes his hand like a dead fish." A weak handshake is considered an indication of a weak character in American society.

In general, the examples I have given demonstrate the need to study the features of both verbal and non-verbal communication. This knowledge is extremely necessary for specialists in the field of teaching language, who have to practice the interaction of people of different cultures.

When men meet in business, they always shake hands. Women have recently begun to greet one other in this manner, particularly in the professional sphere. It should be emphasised, however, that handshaking is more common among younger women than among older women. Almost all Americans perceive the handshake as a required component of the dating ritual, independent of gender or communication standing of the interlocutors; yet, while the majority believe that both men and women can begin this gesture, they always try to initiate the handshake themselves. Americans feel that the handshake should be firm but not painful to the other person. The majority of Americans believe that the male and female handshakes are identical. Today, a woman can shake hands with a guy when they meet, while who is the first to offer a hand (a male or a woman) is not emphasised among Americans, i.e. it is not considered as a communication privilege. The American handshake is remote; they shake hands at arms - length. Generally, the American handshake is a predominantly male gesture that is far less prevalent in Russian conversation.

9. KISS

While greeting, all Americans kiss their friends and family without mentioning their gender. Surprisingly, when asked how often they felt "social kissing" was employed while greeting, half of Americans said it never happened among males and is extremely infrequent among women. At the same time, they

consider a kiss (one-two times) on the cheek to be a "social kiss". In addition to greetings, "social kiss" may be used in situations of farewell, congratulations and compliments. Often when parting, especially for a long time, a farewell is accompanied by light hugs and kisses, while both men and women kiss each other. The host or hostess can kiss a Russian guest 3 times (as they say - "in Russian").

10. HUGS

In the situation of greeting most Americans hug friends and relatives, regardless of their gender. Close friends (regardless of gender) often hug each other goodbye. New acquaintances can also hug goodbye. But this is a new custom and can sometimes be seen as a manifestation of bad taste.

Let us now present a generalized systematic description of the main features of American and Russian communicative behaviour in comparison (Table 2.1). For this, we will use a parametric model for describing nonverbal communicative behaviour.

Table 2.1. Comparative Description of Russian and American Communication Behavior (Parametric Model)

COMMUNICATION DISTANCE		
Options	Russian Communication Behaviour	American Communication Behaviour
<i>Distance of communication</i>	Short	Great
<i>Desire to shorten the distance</i>	Expressed	Weakly expressed
PHYSICAL CONTACT		
<i>Physical contact of interlocutors</i>	Often	Unusual
CORRELATION OF VERBAL AND NON-VERBAL COMMUNICATIONS		
<i>Permissibility of using eye contact instead of verbal greeting</i>	unacceptable	Acceptable

<i>The desire to replace speech with gestures and facial expressions during communicating</i>	low	low
<i>The desire to replace speech with gestures during rapid speech</i>	lowered	Lowered
<i>The desire to replace speech with gestures in emotional speech</i>	lowered	Lowered
GESTICULATION		
<i>Intensity of gesticulation</i>	increased	Moderate
<i>Swipe gesticulation</i>	wide amplitude	narrow amplitude
<i>Emotionality of gestures</i>	increased	Moderate
MIMIC		
<i>Intensity</i>	high	Moderate
<i>Sincerity</i>	high	Moderate
<i>The spontaneity of facial expressions</i>	high	Low
<i>The intensity of facial expressions when expressing an attitude towards the interlocutor</i>	conspicuous	Conspicuous
<i>The intensity of facial expressions expressing gratitude</i>	conspicuous	Conspicuous
VOLUME		
<i>Conversation volume</i>	conspicuous	High
<i>The ability to increase the volume of speech</i>	high	Reduced
SPEED OF COMMUNICATION		

<i>Ability to increase the rate of speech</i>	conspicuous	Conspicuous
<i>The speed of the conversation</i>	average	Average

To sum up, nonverbal communication is a very common and important part in intercultural exchange, especially in TFL. It is necessary to get knowledge of the part and make a full use of it in order to develop language proficiency.

2.3. Pragmatic difficulties in application of nonverbal means in communication

We have analyzed some performance of pragmatic failure, through the analysis, it can be seen that cross-cultural pragmatic failure was caused by a number of factors. There are language mistakes and cultural differences, but the failures caused by cultural differences accounted for a dominant reign. People from different cultural backgrounds have great differences in terms of values, morals, customs, beliefs, ways of thinking and so on, which resulted in a diversity of pragmatic failures. In addition, cultural migration and cultural prejudices of communicators in the cultural communication process are also the causes of pragmatic failures. Here, we will make a simple analysis of the reasons.

Differences in Religious Beliefs

Religion is an important part of human thought. Ethnic groups are different, then religious and cultural beliefs are different. Russians and Americans have some differences in religious terms. Religious belief refers to unshakable conviction and the conversion of the heart and soul of people who profess a particular religion to the sacred object (including the specific teachings and doctrines, etc.). This faith and conversion of heart and soul performs in specific rituals and religious activities and is used to guide and regulate their own behaviour in a secular society. It belongs to particular social ideologies and cultural phenomena.

Except for the broad worship of Mammon and the worldwide cult of Disney, there is no official state religion in America. Americans have the freedom to practise whichever religion they want. Conscience freedom has progressed to the point that you can even create your own religion. Religion can be started by anybody. The Constitution forbids the promotion of religion, and religion is strictly separated from politics. It is banned to recite prayers at school graduations, and no city council should spend even a penny of municipal cash on a mock-up of the stall where Christ was born on Christmas.

In the so-called Bible Belt, which begins somewhere around the southern part of the East Coast and extends somewhere around Missouri or Kansas, small independent sects grow like cotton bushes; they all usually preach variations on their favourite themes: evolution is nonsense, hell awaits sinners, the Lord loved America more than anyone else.

However, the most influential church of American origin remains the Church of Latter-Day Saints from Utah, also known as the Mormon sect, which has millions of followers around the world, and more and more.

Americans adore the notion that if something bad happens to them, the rest of the world will perish. So, every now and then, someone begins shouting about the impending end of the world, usually based on a novel mathematical approach to the Apocalypse or the observation of some strange gunk in the sky by astronomers. This may sometimes lead to widespread frenzy, with everyone flocking to the True Faith in order to get a nice seat in the previous Super Bowl.

Almost all Russians have the same belief and almost the same religion—Christianity, which includes a variety of Christian denominations. As Russia's main religion, Christianity is deeply implanted into Russian culture. Its values, outlook on life, and concept of time are all with Christian -defined brand. So, in Russian culture, some of the idioms and proverbs are also concerned with God, such as “Бог терпел и нам велел.”, and “Жить, как у Христа за пазухой.” The characters and the stories in the Bible after a long time of spread are known to every family and have become an important source of Russian idioms - "Жить –

Богу служить". It has been associated with the Russian culture and language. Some people even said, if you do not understand the Bible, you will not understand Slovenian culture.

Differences in Ways of Thinking

The way of thinking dominates a person's words and deeds, and it is the inherent pattern of brain activity. The way of thinking is relatively finalized, and it has custom-oriented, traditional oriented features in the thinking pattern and thinking structure in the social rational activities. It penetrates into various areas of people's lives, emotional and behavioural methods, and guides and restricts people's words and deeds. The way of thinking also has a relative variability. Cultural backgrounds are different, they will vary widely. The interference caused by differences in ways of thinking is the important reason for pragmatic failures in intercultural communication.

English is a space-based structure, emphasizing rigor and indirect expression. In order to ensure the integrity of the form, English sentence elements are generally not omitted.

There is no one way to define the Russian way of thinking, but one of its characteristic features is what the Russians call *Avos'* (АВОСЬ).

The word *Avos'* has a very long history in the Russian language and can be loosely translated as "maybe" or "hopefully." It expresses a hope that one will be able to avoid negative consequences when taking a risk or doing something improperly. In other words, it describes the tendency to leave things to chance and hope for the best even when a task is completed sloppily or something is left unfinished.

Russians are quite aware of their own tendency for risk-taking or sloppiness. They use the expression "the Russian *Avos'*" (Русский авось) to describe this Russian approach to doing things. Russians often look at the big picture and try to be creative and inventive in the process as opposed to following a strict structure and getting all the details right from start to finish.

In summary, the different ways of thinking created a different language structure model. In cross-cultural communication, pragmatic failures tend to be

caused by their ways of thinking as a standard to communicate of the two parties, which leads to misunderstanding each other. To make the message recipient clearly understand the willingness to express themselves not only is related to the accuracy of the information available, but also should pay attention to organize the information conforming to their ways of thinking.

Value Disparities

The Declaration of Human Rights lays forth the fundamental American values of life, freedom, and the American dream. Many authors describe the United States as a "civilization of businesspeople." Thus, some of the most fundamental ideas of American civilisation are centered on money and economic success, which may be regarded as the most significant values for Americans. These ideals, in fact, determine the whole structure of American society. However, two more American cultural values arise from the idiosyncrasies of the American political and economic systems: the fetishization of trade liberalization and the protection of human freedoms in one's own country and throughout the globe. It's tough not to mention American patriotism, certain that all good comes from America and that America is the lighthouse of world civilization. American justice is equated with equal opportunity. This concept has gotten a lot of attention. D. Rawls' book "The Theory of Justice" powerfully displays the American view of justice as discrepancy justice.

Western cultural value is individualism. It is based on a market economy and capitalist relations of production. It is an individual standard of value. It emphasizes personal values, interests and dignity. Self-realization and self-development and even personal time and space have become its very strong and prominent feature.

The values of Russian civilisation differ slightly from the standards of American culture. Russian culture has significant traditions of community and collectivism. If an American is preoccupied with individual accomplishment, a Russian patriot is not only concerned with collective accomplishment in international competition, but also with the feat of the people. Individual

achievement is a component of general success, not an end in itself. Russian patriotism is the patriotism of the state idea, not of human rights; thus, state power, which includes military power, tends to take a more significant place in Russian national pride than in American one. Justice is frequently defined as equality or social justice, not as equal opportunity, but as almost perfect social, civil, and property equality, which exactly explains the appearance of the socialism and communism phenomenon in Russian civilisation.

From the religious perspective, the concept of work, particularly worldly labour, for the redemption of the soul receives far less focus in Orthodox Christianity than in Protestantism. In Russia, the political regime was the ultimate expression of the worship of work, and it was on this cult that all Soviet power triumphs were built, whereas in America, labour, and, first and foremost, individual labour, was regarded as the first virtue exclusively in religion.

Thus the one thing we see Americans and Russians share in terms of values is a recognition of the importance of hard work in order to achieve success in life. But, even here American hard work is explained by religion and the desire to achieve personal goals, while in Russia, work is part of the common cause, serving the state and society.

Outcomes of the second chapter

A cross-cultural analysis of nonverbal means of communication in the English and Russian languages showed that there are a lot of differences grounded in cultural specificity in the perception of the world. Thus while formulating ideas in the English language we should take into consideration these differences to be proficient in communication.

We should teach national specific elements of nonverbal communication in the English classrooms. In our opinion, the inclusion of a nonverbal means of communication in the context of teaching English involves:

- 1) the definition of nonverbal means of communication from the positions of various cultures;
- 2) the formation of nonverbal behaviour through mastery of strategies (operations and complex actions) since they are a form of implementing a communicative style;
- 3) modelling situations of interaction through speech acts and stable style parameters in the studied linguistic cultures;
- 4) the adequate usage of nonverbal means of communication according to the norms of the studied linguistic culture.

To sum up this section we can say that the mastery of the nonverbal communication of the people of the language being studied is important during the development of communicative competence with a focus on its pragmatic (linguistic and intercultural) aspects. There are great communication challenges among various cultures, such as language differences, nonverbal signs, cultural context and internal communication in multicultural company and so on. However, it does not mean that people in different cultures are standing in absolutely opposite sides. In order to get a successful communication, we could vary communication styles along with the changes of different situations and interpersonal relations while going on a communication. We are sure that the mastery of the culturally marked repertoire of the nonverbal means of communication of the people and identifying specific elements contribute to an adequate understanding and prediction of communicative behaviour.

CHAPTER III. TECHNOLOGY OF TEACHING NONVERBAL MEANS AT ENGLISH CLASSES

3.1. Ways of teaching nonverbal means of communication

Nonverbal language proficiency is essential not only for communication but also for the development their own cultural identity, a ws well as of attitude toward native speakers, their culture and way of life. Students of foreign languages should become acquainted with the linguistic units that most clearly convey the national characteristics of the people's culture - the native speaker and the environment in which they live. Mastering a foreign language is inextricably linked to mastering the national culture, which entails not only the acquisition of cultural knowledge (cultural facts), but also the development of the ability and willingness to comprehend the mentalities of native speakers of the language being studied, as well as the specificities of this country's communicative behaviour. The language of everyday behaviour is particularly essential in this regard.

The model of teaching created by us is built on the basis of intercultural approach which was described thoroughly by Makhkamova [2010]. Teaching of strategies of communicative style must be based of certain principles, which are determined by us as following:

- strategic character of communicative style;
- cross-cultural features;
- functional value;
- sociocultural and situational adequacy;
- strategic effectiveness

These principles were formulated taking into consideration some principles of G.T. Makhkamova [2010] and principles suggested by N.A. Skurihin [2012].

The selection and systematization of the content of language material are based on a set of principles: *systemic, phased / multi-level, professional orientation (intersubject communications), modularity, information content, impact on the affective sphere of the individual*. Accounting and implementation of content

structuring principles are centred on the development of a teacher of vocational training's whole set of communication abilities.

The consistency principle enables the creation of material that is cohesive while also successfully applying management influences to each content component.

The implementation of **the phasing / multi-level work concept** is arranged at all levels of education, which adds to the steady growth of professional knowledge that serves the speaking skills as well as comprehending the material. The phasing principle is connected to the development of logical and informational abilities since the algorithm for their development purposely varies in accordance with the level of complexity of a given task.

The third **content selection principle** is the professional orientation principle, which is implemented through multidisciplinary links. Broadening of the professional knowledge, which is part of vocational training speech and logical-compositional abilities may be reached through viewing interdisciplinary linkages.

Another principle of structuring content is the **principle of modularity**. In the process of learning with elements of modular technology, the individualization of the learning process is ensured, and the quality of independent learning activities is improved, which ultimately leads to the development of all groups of communicative skills of a teacher of vocational training.

The concept of **informativeness**, which indicates the sufficiency, correctness, and fullness of information required for arranging a professional discourse between a teacher and pupils, is the second principle of content selection.

The principles of informativity and affecting the emotive dimension of the personality are inextricably linked. Every difficulty level's material contains components that have a positive impact on the development of productive and behavioural spheres. Furthermore, actions that create the emotional domain are conceivable on the basis of any text, necessitating an emotive response to what is read.

One facet of communication culture is the alignment of nonverbal communication methods with the goals and content of verbal information transfer. This interaction is especially important for a teacher who combines verbal and nonverbal communication in work.

The development of socio-cultural awareness is unachievable without using culturally specified nonverbal tools in the educational process that enhance socio-cultural awareness. This idea holds that the selection of instructional materials should be guided by **the principle of cultural orientation**.

The advantage of using this method to choose nonverbal means of communication in order to integrate them into the educational process is based on a phenomenon known as nonverbal homonymy. This concept emphasises the similarities of nonverbal communication meanings and practises in the native and studied languages. The concept of cultural orientation is used to distinguish nonverbal modalities of communication that are important from the perspective of foreign language teaching methods. These components are only tested receptively and do not require any additional interpretations. Many nonverbal behaviours, such as emotive expressions, are now commonly considered to be inherited. The instructor faces a difficult task: separating the culturally determined movements that distinguish representatives of various cultures. The notion of cultural orientation is used as a differentiating mechanism to identify nonverbal modes of communication that are significant from the aspect of foreign language teaching methods. The instructor faces a difficult task: distinguishing within a wide variety of bodily motions the culturally defined gestures typical of representatives of the nation of the language being studied.

The combination of nonverbal behaviour patterns produces the result of "nonverbal interaction" [Labunskaya, 1999, p. 42]. The measures mentioned above seem to be the most accurate transmitters of the "national character" of people and the country whose language is being researched. The established norms for governing behavioural strategies are encoded in the gestural, visual, distant, and tactile nonverbal codes, representing the uniqueness and dissimilarity of the

researched culture. Restraint of character, for example, is shown in the lack of sweeping gestures among Americans, and the value of private space is manifested in the need to maintain a geographic distance throughout a conversation. Thus, the incorporation of a nonverbal semiotic code into the practice of teaching foreign languages should occur on the basis of a cultural mirror image, i.e., taking into consideration the connection characteristic - atypical. The **cultural orientation principle** allows us to identify a collection of nonverbal communication methods that are appropriate for the methodological goals.

Following the **principle of functionality** means that the object of assimilation should not be non-verbal means in themselves, but the functions they perform. So, for example, the handshake gesture conveys information about the situation of greeting or farewell, the extension of the thumb is associated with the function of counting or pointing, etc. Not the language itself, but the functioning, in our case, of non-verbal means in actual communicative acts, is taken as a basis. The principle of functionality is associated with the pragmatic orientation of the methodology of teaching foreign languages. The amount of these funds should reflect the specifics of the functioning of these kinemas in life situations. We are talking about the "practical value" of non-verbal means. In other words, the ability to read and interpret a non-verbal signal correctly is at the forefront. Some information should be transmitted to the participants in the intercultural dialogue with a non-verbal message, within the principle of functionality, the response to which must be necessary. Common to such responses is the adequacy of the information received, based on etiquette principles. It may represent some action or inaction; it may be as verbal as a non-verbal response.

Nonverbal means frequently supplement or replace etiquette norms of speech in the communication process. Speech etiquette is defined as "a system of communicative tropes, established expressions that help to create, maintain, and break contact between people who speak," and it is used "in direct contact communication, which is saturated with nonverbal components and techniques. It is important to identify which nonverbal means are being prompted by the use of

speech etiquette principles in the choosing of the type and amplitude.” [Formanovskaya, 2010, p. 4].

Since the rules of speech etiquette permeate all areas of communication, the study of the etiquette norms of a country with a different socio-cultural reality becomes an indispensable component of the methodology of teaching a foreign language. According to A.A. Akishina and N.I. Formanovskaya, there are several areas of use of speech etiquette: request, acquaintance, apology, appeal, greeting, farewell etc. It is important to consider the hierarchy of relations between the addresser and the addressee, the degree of formality of the communication environment, age and the degree of an acquaintance while choosing the appropriate etiquette units. Traditionally, the field of etiquette models of behaviour has the largest number of culturally determined kinemas thus in the process of mastering a foreign language, etiquette formulas of speech are studied, while non-verbal etiquette manifestations remain out of focus.

Knowledge of nationally specific rules of non-verbal etiquette behaviour is as important for mastering communication as the actual language rules are important for constructing a speech. “Ignoring, not knowing or misinterpreting them can lead to misunderstanding, failure and, often, culture shock.” [Eremeeva, 2011. p.22].

Communication between people, and in particular between representatives of different cultures, is regulated by the norms adopted in a particular society. This dictates the need to follow the principle of status in the implementation of interaction both on the verbal and non-verbal levels. Full-fledged communication is impossible without observing **the principles of morality and politeness**, which form the basis of a tolerant attitude towards the interlocutor and contribute to the development of empathy.

Selecting material for mastering in the process of teaching the norms of adequate communication in the country of the language being studied, is extremely important. The named principle provides for taking into account the social status of the individual, which is understood as “the relative position of a person in the

social system, including rights and obligations and the resulting mutual expectations of behaviour” [Eremeeva, 2011. p. 3].

As Yu.E. Prokhorov, “having a substantial (independent and learned characteristics - nationality, gender, cultural and social origin) dimension, the status is considered at the level of social distance and the level of normativity” [Nogaeva, 2006. p. 37]. So, for example, in American culture, when shaking hands, the woman, the eldest in age and the representative of the highest position (leader) is the first to shake hands. The need for the correct choice and adequate use of non-verbal means is due to the fact that "non-verbal status indices are of priority in normal communication" [Karasik, 2005. p. 287].

Taking into account the principle of status allows you to pay attention to the manifestation of personality traits in the implementation of social status. On this occasion, Yu.E. Prokhorov notes: "... in addition to the implementation of socially determined rights and obligations, a person seeks to express his status with his own, specific features of his non-verbal manifestation" [Nogaeva, 2006. p. 33].

The presence and implementation of nonverbal units makes it possible to determine which foreign cultural society the interlocutor belongs to, to "see" the speaker's social status, to recognise the situation of speech etiquette, taking into account the addressee's position, and to interpret the information received in intercultural communication. As a result, mastery of a set of culturally specified nonverbal language indicators should occur throughout the course of learning a foreign language as a guarantee of full participation in intercultural conversation.

As communication between representatives of different cultures is impossible without a conscious understanding and knowledge of cultural differences that appear in the system of non-verbal means, non-verbal means should be moved from the category of an alternative to that of a constant of the learning process.

Taking into account socio-cultural factors helps to eliminate typical interaction errors and misunderstandings. Following the socio-cultural approach to teaching a foreign language makes it possible to include “non-verbal means of every day and etiquette communication in the educational process, to identify

specific features of the national character, and to use them in the course of mastering students the methods of non-verbal speech communication.” [Eremeeva, 2011. p.52].

As a result, putting the principles of nonverbal means selection into practise creates a real possibility for their active use in the process of teaching a foreign language. The development of these tools helps communicants to use all of the mechanisms of a different linguoculture in an intercultural communication setting, allowing them to accept and grasp the surrounding reality and perform particular pragmatic problems.

Satisfaction of human needs is initially possible only if he enters into communication, interacting with other people. This gives rise to the subject's need to tell them about what is important and meaningful to him. [Passov, 1991. p.140]

Teaching a foreign language, knowledge includes, first of all, language knowledge and knowledge of national culture. Communicative movements include the so-called kinemas, or automated movements, which are distinguished by a direct connection with a speech message. Complement and replace speech actions. Particularly noteworthy are kinemas that do not match in performance with coinciding meanings in the communicative behaviour of native speakers of Russian and English, as well as those gestures that can and even need to be used during an English lesson. Of interest is a small group of kinemas that do not coincide in meaning with the same performance. For example, in the American tradition, the 'hit hands' gesture is associated with situations of greeting and farewell. In Russian culture, this gesture has the meaning - make a deal; the gesture 'snapping fingers' in the American tradition is associated with attracting attention, which is sometimes used by students in order to attract the attention of the teacher. In the Russian tradition, the meaning of this gesture is an expression of mistake and annoyance. In foreign language lessons, you can use the gesture of tapping the knuckles on the table, which in Western European countries traditionally expresses a greeting from teachers, as well as expressions of approval and satisfaction from a

brilliantly read lecture. The above communicative movements can be used to some extent in an English lesson.

Thus, non-verbal behaviour is communicatively and nationally conditioned and should be taken into account when learning a foreign language. However, not everyone understands that sign language is not a universal language and often transfers sign symbols from one culture to another, as a result of which communication does not take place or is difficult. When teaching the culture of non-verbal communication, one cannot ignore the psycho-physiological symptoms of the emotional state and non-communicative movements. A Russian student who wants to speak in the class raises his hand, stretching out his hand, while an American raises two fingers.

We've divided the exercises on teaching the understanding and use of non-verbal means of communication into 2 groups: exercises on understanding and exercises in the use of gestures as a representative of a particular culture.

1 group - exercises on understanding

1. Films

Another practicable way of teaching both verbal and non-verbal communication is using film where excellent examples of intercultural communication are depicted. Damnet highlighted that presenting films in EL classes can considerably increase learners' acquisition of non-verbal competence along with increasing their appreciation and understanding of the native speaker standards in other aspects of their communication [Chastain, 1988. p.122]. As stated by him, films contain culturally and publically constructed depictions of human experience that may not thoroughly replicate daily life, as well as films, represent realistic language in realistic settings, and also clearly reveal meanings of words and expressions along with depicting some hidden meanings beyond the spoken language, such as body language, facial expressions and gestures. Nevertheless, no film is consistently valuable for ELT aims all the way through so that teacher is required to judge how to select clips that are appropriate to the point of learning. Many movies portray social awkwardness and miscommunication that

come about when a person acts informal in a formal situation, or vice versa [Damnet, 2008. p.15]. For example, humour may lead to miscomprehensions, because in some cultures humour is applied intentionally informal settings to lessen tension, whereas in other cultures such behaviour is considered totally offensive.

For illustration, we may take the movies such as:

- “The Proposal” 2009 American romantic comedy,
- “The Devil wears Prada” 2006 American comedy-drama,
- “Mean Girls” 2004 American teen comedy film which demonstrate American style of self-presenting and may serve as vivid examples of the ones where individualistic societies are artistically revealed. It is known, that the members of individualistic society value independence and self-sufficiency while the members of collectivist society value group involvement when it comes to making decisions or achieving goals. In our opinion, learners can be shown an initial part in an adventure film. The teacher should ask the students to guess what might happen afterwards, with the option of screening the next scene with or without a sound. Students would then be requested for more predictions.

The first group will be shown the video without sound and asked to make a prediction of what might be said, whereas a second group listens only to the sound and attempts to find out what images might be going on the screen Learners also will watch native speakers on a short video with the purpose of focusing on features of non-verbal communication. (see **Appendix 3**)

2. Exercise "Pantomime"

The group is divided into two subgroups, both groups receive a sheet with words (a different list of words). The words are written on separate cards. One representative from group "A" draws one card, and one word and depicts it. The other group has to guess the word. Then a participant from group "B" demonstrates the word that he will pull out. You can naturally depict not only words but entire scenes.

3. Exercise "Broken VCR"

The participants sit in a circle. The task is given - to convey the emotional state of, using only non-verbal means. The state passes from one participant to the next in a circle. The rest sit with their eyes closed. When each of the groups has received and transmitted the state, the first sender compares what he received with what he transmitted.

After the game, the participants should have a desire to understand what non-verbal communication is, and how to decipher and understand others by posture, gestures, and facial expressions. The facilitator provides such information and lists the elements of non-verbal communication (voice timbre and intonation, pupil width; space separating speakers, breathing rate; gestures, body movements; posture; clothing; facial expression; status symbol; eye contact, etc.)

The following types of exercises exercise may be used as a warming up activity and may help students to consider the means of non-verbal communication in more detail, determine their role and learn how to use the means of non-verbal communication.

4. Picture exercise

Compare both pictures. What role do facial expressions and gestures play? After the discussion, give the students brief information about the zones and territories, eye contact. (see **Appendix 3**)

5. Exercise "Mimicry"

Look at the emotion patterns and think about which feeling each pattern expresses.

The following expressions are given in the diagrams:

1. hostile,
2. sarcastic,
3. joyful,
4. evil, angry,
5. sad, gloomy,
6. tired,
7. skeptical,

8. calm, neutral.

Information is given on the meaning of facial expressions in non-verbal communication.

6. Exercise "Impression"

List the impression foreigners might have of you if you are keeping eye contact, and speak in a raised or annoyed tone.

Answer options:

- you are tired of everything;
- you are not interested in your social circle;
- you are not friendly;
- You don't respect others.
- You are scared.

Further, students are provided with information about the meaning of some gestures (arms crossed on the chest, the "lion" pose, etc.).

7. Exercise "Look"

Demonstrate your view of the interlocutor:

- with reproach,
- with a strong ban
- with boundless surprise
- with anger
- pending further action.

The significance of the gaze in the technique of communication is discussed. A recommendation is given: how to behave in a demon with a representative of American culture. This information will make you feel more confident and allow you to focus.

8 Brain storming Topics

1. Why is nonverbal language such a fertile field for miscommunication?
2. What is the difference between the distances at which Americans and Russians commonly stand when talking to each other?
3. How do Americans and Russians react towards silences in conversation?

4. What is the difference in American and Russian attitudes toward smiling? Toward staring at people?
5. How do Americans and Russians differ in terms of crying or showing their feelings at an event such as a funeral?
6. How does an American feel if a woman offers him a “limp paw”? What is this called in English?
7. How do Russians and Americans differ in terms of embraces on meeting and parting?
8. Explain the meaning of the following American gestures:
 - a) The index finger and thumb are joined to form a circle.
 - b) Wiping the hand across the forehead.
 - c) Third finger is crossed over the index finger.
 - d) The palm is raised and moved back and forth sideways.
9. What is the difference between the way Russians and Americans count on their fingers?
10. Why do Americans find the gesture of shaking the index finger up and down offensive?
11. Discuss three other gestures which Americans may not understand or find insulting.
12. How is the American approach of “positive thinking” shown in the attitude toward the Russian gestures "spread your hands" or "put your hands down"?
13. Write a dialogue in English showing what took place in the courtroom between the woman insisting that her neighbor wanted to kill her, the emigre banging the garbage can lid, and the professor explaining the meaning of the gesture "run your hand down your throat".

Group 2 - exercises in the use of gestures as a representative of a particular culture.

1. Role Play

Through different role plays learners practice what it is like to be diverse, to be looked on strangely, to be criticized or even expelled. They will also realize

basic behavioural norms, lifestyle, etc. Role plays enable learners to control their cultural fear and provide opportunities for oral communication [Chastain, 1988. p.157]. The students can learn verbal and non-verbal features of communication interactively. consequently bringing together both mind and body and reinstating the balance between physical and intellectual aspects of learning, what is more, they develop learners' ability to empathize with others and so become better communicators. All kinds of drama, presentations, debates and interviews can be regarded as the types of role plays. It is particularly important to make a debriefing discussion with the group after each role-plays in order to raise learners' awareness of what happened during the «game». Eliciting from the participants what they have exposed while playing; how they were able to visualize the norms of their allotted 'new identity; and whether their character was authentic or stereotypical - will enable them to reflect on their experience.

2. Dialogues

- Practice using a scripted dialogue. Pairs of students rehearsed parts, then acted out the dialogue using expressions, gestures and posture.
- Learners act out a dialogue using gesture and expression only
- Learners, in pairs, take turns in listening to each other for 30 seconds, using only non-verbal responses.

3. Exercise "Greeting"

Students greet each other in America with 10 shades: fear, pleasure, discipline, surprise, reproach, joy, displeasure, dignity, irony and indifference.

There is a space around each of us that we strive to keep intact. The resulting tension in the process of communication can be an indicator of a violation of space.

Information:

0 - 0.5 m - the intimate distance at which close people communicate;

0.5 - 1.2 m - interpersonal distance for talking to friends;

1.2 - 3.7 m - zone of business relations (head, subordinate).

The information about the rules of greeting in the USA, other countries and about the dominant zones should be given to students.

4. Exercise "How do you say?"

Show how to use gestures to “say” the following:

- "Come in!"
- "There!"
- "Straight!"
- "I don't know!" etc.

5. Exercise "Imitation game" - Who is the candidate for the job?

Have gestures changed? Has emotional state changed?

Rules for interpreting body language: do not snatch a single detail and do not draw far-reaching conclusions from it; take into account the nationality and temperament of a person - for different nations, body language has its own specifics (Brits, Germans, French, Americans).

Everyone knows that non-verbal behaviour is communicatively and nationally conditioned and should be taken into account when learning a foreign language. However, not everyone understands that sign language is not a universal language and often transfers sign symbols from one culture to another, as a result of which communication does not take place or is difficult.

Therefore, the purpose of all these exercises is the following: to teach students non-verbal communication in a team and to acquaint them with the traditions and customs of communication in different countries. As a result, the pupils should communicate more relaxedly in a team, understand the moods and feelings of people through gestures, facial expressions, and postures, and be able to negotiate with different age groups, regardless of their position in society. The lesson is lively, the students communicate with each other and easily make contact. Children are interested in acquiring new knowledge and putting it into practice. These exercises are designed to overcome intercultural barriers in communication.

3.2. Experiment and its results

In order to prove the hypothesis of the current dissertation, there was a need of conducting an experiment. The experimental work was conducted among the

2nd year bachelor's students of Tashkent State Pedagogical University after Nizami.

The experimental training included three phases:

- 1) Organization (hypothesis was developed, the collected material analyzed and systematized to substantiate a working hypothesis, the goal of training and tasks for achieving the goal was determined, a methodology for teaching specific facts of the language was developed);
- 2) Implementation (developed training methodology was tested in the classroom);
- 3) Interpretation (objective and thorough analysis of the results obtained (statistical indicators) and the proposal of relevant recommendations).

The organizational phase included the design of an experimental program for implementation. At this stage it was necessary to carry out the following ***procedures:***

1. Statement of the purpose, tasks, and methods of the organizational phase of the experiment.
2. Identification of the problems and statement of the hypothesis for the experiment.
3. Definition of the purpose, objectives, and conditions of the teaching experiment.
4. Development of didactic materials for implementation.
5. Selection of specific methods for monitoring the assessment of the quality of our proposed technology for teaching communicative style to the 2nd year students. The purpose of the experiment in the organizational phase was to reveal nonverbal communication in the aspect of intercultural communication.

The tasks of the organizational phase were as follows:

- Compiling questionnaires for teachers to identify the issue of their awareness of nonverbal communication and its importance in the development of language and culture proficiency;
- Revealing the current level of nonverbal communication among 2nd-year students;

- Material development for implementation into the educational process.

The hypothesis of the experiment was the level of language proficiency would be improved if we teach nonverbal communication via activities created by us (see in the previous section and in **Appendix 3**).

Verification of the hypothesis in the implementation of the experiment required the following tasks:

1. To design materials for teaching nonverbal communication with correlation with course syllabus materials;
2. To reveal pedagogical conditions under which the implementation of the model can be possible;
3. To conduct a teaching experiment in order to prove the effectiveness of the model of teaching nonverbal aspects of intercultural communication;
4. To develop criteria for assessing the students' pragmatic skills in the context of intercultural nonverbal communication.

Teaching materials for the experiment were chosen in accordance with the level and understanding of the students. Varying conditions of the experiment included: determining students' needs, and the use of developed pre and post questionnaires in the experimental group. The total number of students involved in the experiment was 16. We conducted a questionnaire for the EG group to check their needs and desires for learning intercultural communication. It was given 16 hours to conduct the experiment for one month.

Topics for teaching intercultural nonverbal communication are nonverbal behaviour in the context of different cultures, and cultural specificity of nonverbal communication.

Before starting the most efficient experiment, we choose students for the Control group (CG) and Experimental group (EG). First, we decided to clarify what means of nonverbal communication do teachers use in TEFL (see **Appendix 2**) and then what students know about nonverbal behaviour and what difficulties they face. We have distributed an online questionnaire that consists of 5 questions aimed at clarifying whether there is a need to improve students' nonverbal

communication. There were 16 participants in the group who respectfully answered the questions by putting ticks on the agree/neutral/disagree columns. The obtained quantitative results are provided in Table 3.1 and converted to percentages.

Table 3.1. Results of questionnaire for students based on needs of learning nonverbal aspects of intercultural communication

Nº	Statement	Agree	Neutral	Disagree
1.	I don't understand the specificity nonverbal aspects of intercultural communication	8	5	3
		50%	31.25%	18.75%
2.	I have difficulties in constructing ideas using nonverbal means as native speakers	10	3	3
		62.5%	18.75%	18.75%
3.	I have difficulties in using body language appropriately	10	4	2
		62.5%	25%	12.5%
4.	I have difficulties in using paralinguistic items correctly	8	8	-
		50%	50%	0%
5.	I should learn nonverbal means of communication to improve my communicative competence	12	4	-
		75.00%	25.00%	0%
Overall:		60 %	30 %	10 %

According to the results, of the questionnaire for students based on the needs for learning Nonverbal 60% of students agreed, 30 % were neutral, 10 % disagreed.

After defining students' needs, we started to conduct our experiment part. In this part, we give them the activities created by us (see **Appendix 3**).

The students' final assessment was evaluated in accordance with 50 scores, then their grades were transformed into percent (see **Table 3.2**).

Table 3.2. The results of final test

N	Control Group		Experimental Group	
	Students	Results	Students	Results
1.	ABDUFATTOROVA LOBAR G'AYRAT QIZI	41%	ADXAMOVA SEVINCH ALISHER QIZI	91,5
2.	AVAZBAYEVA MALIKAXON DILMUROD QIZI	57%	BAHODIROVA CHAROS ISOXON QIZI	92%
3.	BOLTABOYEVA MUBINAXON ABDULHAMID QIZI	48%	BOBOBEKOVA SHAHLO BEKZOD QIZI	85%
4.	FAYZIYEV MURODJON FURQATOVICH	38%	FARXADOVA RUXSHANA SANJAR QIZI	82,5%
5.	IMAMOVA AZIZAXON- SABINA RAVSHAN QIZI	75,5%	IBRAGIMOVA SAIDA ALISHER QIZI	81%
6.	LATIFOV DILSHODBEK SOBIRJON-O'G'LI	63%	ISAXAROVA YELENA YUREVNA	85%
7.	MADRAXIMOVA VIOLA SEYDAMETOVNA	88,5%	LI ELZA VIKTOROVNA	87,5%
8.	MIRXAMIDOVA AZIZA ALISHEROVNA	63%	MAMADALIYEVA SAIDAXON ABDUVAXOB QIZI	81%
9.	MUXAMMADALIYEV AZIZJON ABDURASHID O'G'LI.	52%	MUSTAFAYEVA SEVINCH ULUGBEK QIZI	98%
10.	NASIROVA SABINA XONDAMIROVNA	42,5%	NABIYEVA YULDUZXON TEMUROVNA	85%

11.	NIYAZOVA SHIRINBONU XAYAT QIZI	36%	NAZAROVA GO'ZAL IKROM QIZI	78%
12.	O'ROQOVA DIYORA DAVRON QIZI	27%	NUSRATULLAYEV A CHAROS OTABEK QIZI	84,5%
13.	RAHMATULLAYEVA NILUFAR ISOMIDDIN QIZI	41,5%	OZODOVA ASALXON ORIFOVNA	81%
14	RIZAYEVA MAHINA DILSHOD QIZI	34%	RAJABBOYEVA GULRO'Z DILSHOD QIZI	87%
15	SALOXIDDINOVA SEVINCH ABROR QIZI	41%	SHURAYEVA SAMIRA TIMUROVNA	79%
16	YUSUPOVA MADINA OLIMJON QIZI	69%	XUSHBOQOVA POKIZAXON BAXROM QIZI	82.5%
	Average	51%	Average	85 %

As it can be seen from the Table and Figure below, the language performance in the context of appropriacy of nonverbal communication of CG and EG varies greatly. The average score of the test of the control group accounts for only 51 per cent while the group who has been trained in nonverbal means of communication reaches 82.5 per cent on average.

If we analyze it in more detail, in CG almost half of the group (students) gets less than 50%, and another 2 students do only less than 60%. There are some students who showed very poor performance at numbers less than 30% and only one student can get more than 80%. None of the students does the task for Figure 3.1 or more than 89 per cent.

Figure 3.1 Results of the students' achievements in the EG and CG

Talking about EG, more than half of the students show the sophisticated results, at numbers more than 80 per cent (11 students) and more than 90 per cent (3 students). Only 2 out of 16 students get less than 80 %. It is important to note that all the students do the task for As and Bs, as none of them gets lower than 70%.

These results were summarized in the diagram (See **Figure 3.2**) to show the efficacy of the suggested model and the materials of its application.

Figure 3.2. Average scores comparison

These results show the effectiveness of our model of teaching Nonverbal aspects of intercultural communication and the necessity to apply them widely in the local context. The research has been carried in a small scale with only 16 students, thus, further attempts to implement them on a larger scale will be of only benefit for the development of students' intercultural communicative style.

Outcomes of the third chapter

The results of this revealed that there was a strong relationship between the quality, amount and the method of using non-verbal communication by teachers while teaching. Based on the findings of the studies reviewed, it was found that the more the teachers used verbal and non-verbal communication, the more efficacious their education and the students' academic progress were. Under non-verbal communication, some other patterns were used. For example, emotive, work, supportive, imaginative, purposive, and balanced communication using speech, body, and pictures all have been effective in students' learning and academic success. The teachers' attention to the students' non-verbal reactions and arranging the syllabus considering the students' mood and readiness have been emphasized in the studies reviewed.

The research has been carried in a small scale with only 16 students, thus, further attempts to implement them on a larger scale will be of only benefit for the development of students' communicative style.

In order to prove the hypothesis of the current dissertation, there was a need of conducting an experiment. The experimental work was conducted among the 2nd year students of the pedagogical University. The experimental training included three phases:

- 1) Organization (hypothesis was developed, the collected material analyzed and systematized to substantiate a working hypothesis, the goal of training and tasks

for achieving the goal was determined, a methodology for teaching specific facts of the language was developed);

2) Implementation (developed training methodology was tested in the classroom);

3) Interpretation (objective and thorough analysis of the results obtained (statistical indicators) and the proposal of relevant recommendations).

It can be seen from the quantitative analysis that the language performance in the context of appropriacy of the nonverbal aspects of communication of CG and EG varies greatly. The average score of the test of the control group accounts for only 51 per cent while the group that has been trained in nonverbal communication reaches 85 per cent on average.

These results show the effectiveness of our model of teaching nonverbal communication in the contexts of different cultures and the necessity to apply them widely in the local context. The research has been carried in a small scale with only 18 students, thus, further attempts to implement them on a larger scale will be of only benefit for the development of students' intercultural communication.

CONCLUSION

Having analyzed existing research and experiments in the sphere of nonverbal communication within the context of different cultures, the researcher has concluded that in achieving expected outcomes, the current teaching context is highly in need of teaching nonverbal means for improving language proficiency.

The research consisted of several stages, starting from thoroughly investigating the works being done so far in linguistics and intercultural communication, related to the study of nonverbal behaviour, nonverbal means and teaching nonverbal communication within intercultural communication. These materials helped to collect necessary data for further research and fund theoretical knowledge on the point. The next step was to tackle the issue of defining the approaches and methods of teaching nonverbal communication to learn from the experiences of previous researchers. Eventually, the required data been collected and examined research came to its primary point and goal – designing a model of teaching nonverbal means of communication through the prism of various cultures. In designing the model several factors such as the needs of research subjects, their preferences and needs and essentially, research hypotheses have been taken into consideration.

The new model developed by the researcher is based on the theory of nonverbal communicative behaviour, the hypothesis about cultural specificity of nonverbal means of the native speakers and activities for training nonverbal communication suggested by foreign educators. According to this model, learners need to practice nonverbal communication by items defined in the content of teaching to become proficient intercultural speakers.

The next step was implementing the model into the context and designing respective activities to train students` nonverbal communicative behaviour.

In the research, it was found that the work on nonverbal communication significantly improved the academic achievement of the second-year students in the context of appropriacy of the nonverbal aspects of communication of CG. The intensity of the study and the systematic instruction of teaching nonverbal

communication in the contexts of different cultures led to positive effects on the improvement of general communicative competence.

The suggested model and material for its implementation have been approved among the 2nd year bachelor's students of Tashkent State Pedagogical University after Nizami and proved its efficacy.

To prove the hypothesis of the current dissertation, there was a need of experimenting. The experimental training included three phases: organization, Implementation and Interpretation.

Quantitative and qualitative data processing showed the effectiveness of our model of teaching nonverbal communication in the context of culture and the necessity to apply them widely in the local context. The research has been carried in a small scale with only 16 students thus, further attempts to implement them on a larger scale will be of only benefit for the development of students' nonverbal intercultural communication.

To conclude, nonverbal communication must be an object of teaching foreign languages following the given domains. The suggested activities are effective so they can be used in the practice of teaching English.

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Online Materials:

1. <https://culturalatlas.sbs.com.au/countries>
2. <https://www.scienceofpeople.com/quiz/>

APPENDIX

Appendix#1

Scheme 1. Classification of non-verbal means of communication

Table 2. Mimic codes of emotional states (according to V. A. Labunskaya)

Parts and elements of the face	Emotional states					
	Anger	Contempt	Suffering	Fear	Astonishment	Joy
Position of the mouth	Mouth open	Mouth closed		Mouth open		Usually Mouth closed
Lips	The corners of the lips are down			The corners of the lips are raised		
Eye shape	Eyes open or narrowed	Eyes narrowed		Eyes open wide		Eyes narrowed or open
Eye brightness	Eyes shine	Eyes are dull		not pronounced eyes shine		Eyes shine
Eyebrow position	Eyebrows are pushed to the bridge of the nose			Eyebrows raised		
Eyebrow corners	The outer corners of the eyebrows are raised up			The inner corners of the eyebrows are raised up		
Forehead	Vertical folds on the forehead and bridge of the nose			Horizontal folds on the forehead		
Mobility of the face and its parts	Dynamic face			Frozen face		Dynamic face

Questionnaire

Please answer the following questions by crossing the relevant box.

Section A – Personal Information

This section of the questionnaire refers to personal information. Please kindly provide the following information. Your cooperation is highly appreciated.

1. Gender:

Male Female

2. Age:

21-25 26-30 31-35 36-40 41 and over

3. Teaching Experience: 0-5 6-10 11–15 16 and over 4. Level of Education: A.A. B.A. M.A. Ph.D.

Section B – Nonverbal Communication Skills

To what extent do you actually use the following nonverbal communication skills in your EFL classrooms? Please go through the items carefully and select the item by crossing the appropriate box. Use the following 5-point scale where:

1. = Very Little (VL) 2. = A Little (AL) 3. = Somewhat (SW)
 4. = Much (M) 5. = Very Much (VM)

I: Kinesics:

No	Items	VL	AL	SW	M	VM
1	Nodding head	1	2	3	4	5
2	Shaking head	1	2	3	4	5

3	Extending open palms to class	1	2	3	4	5
4	Using hands, arms, shoulders, and head to gesture to students	1	2	3	4	5
5	Moving about the classroom	1	2	3	4	5

II: Posture:

No	Items	VL	AL	SW	M	VM
6	Having a direct body position and facial orientation	1	2	3	4	5
7	Having a relaxed and open body position	1	2	3	4	5
8	Leaning forward toward students	1	2	3	4	5
9	Maintaining an erect body posture	1	2	3	4	5

III: Facial Expressions:

No	Items	VL	AL	SW	M	VM
10	Smiling at students	1	2	3	4	5
11	Frowning at students	1	2	3	4	5
12	Using proper facial expressions	1	2	3	4	5

	according to the need and situation					
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IV: Proxemics:

No	Items	VL	AL	SW	M	VM
13	Sitting close to students	1	2	3	4	5
14	Standing close to students	1	2	3	4	5
15	Walking toward students	1	2	3	4	5

V: Haptics:

No	Items	VL	AL	SW	M	VM
16	Shaking hands with students	1	2	3	4	5
17	Touching students on the arm	1	2	3	4	5
18	Touching students on the head	1	2	3	4	5
19	Touching students on the shoulder	1	2	3	4	5
20	Touching students on the back	1	2	3	4	5

VI: Oculistics:

No	Items	VL	AL	SW	M	VM
21	Staring at	1	2	3	4	5

	student					
22	Keeping regular and proper eye contact	1	2	3	4	5

VII: Paravocalics:

No	Items	VL	AL	SW	M	VM
23	Utilizing silence	1	2	3	4	5
24	Varying stress	1	2	3	4	5
25	Speaking clearly					
26	Varying voice volume	1	2	3	4	5
27	Varying rate of speech	1	2	3	4	5
28	Using rise and fall in the voice	1	2	3	4	5

VIII: Chronemics:

No	Items	VL	AL	SW	M	VM
29	Being punctual and regular	1	2	3	4	5
30	Pacing the lesson (Finishing the lesson on time)	1	2	3	4	5
31	Waiting to listen to student responses	1	2	3	4	5

Thank you for taking the time to complete this questionnaire.

Lesson plans and activities

Topic: Nonverbal communication

Time Required: 50–120 minutes

Objectives:

1. The students will develop an awareness of nonverbal communication after watching three video clips.
2. The students will be able to identify different types of non-verbal communication after watching three video clips and having a discussion with their class mates.
3. The students will be able to improve their communication skills by applying their knowledge of non-verbal communication to future personal, academic and/or work-related situations.

Materials:

- Non-Verbal Communication YouTube video clips
- Non-Verbal Communication worksheet,
- Writing Guidelines/Rubrics,
- Group Work Evaluation.

Process:

1. Introduce the term Non-Verbal Communication. Ask students what they think that means?
 - Have them give you examples of each of type of nonverbal communication:
 - ✓ Hand and Body Gestures,

- ✓ Facial Expressions,

✓ Body Postures,

✓ Eye Contact,

✓ Personal Space.

2. Preview and select three YouTube video clips listed in resources. After students have finished viewing all three of the video clips, put the students in to groups of 3-4. Give each group a copy of the worksheet (see Table#1). Have the group fill out the chart by listing the nonverbal communication examples they observed in the videos. Have them list the examples into their appropriate categories as listed on the worksheet: Facial Expressions, Hand and Body Gestures, Body Postures, Eye Contact & Personal Space.

3. Once the chart is completed have the groups share their results with the class. Have each student answer the following question in writing.

- ✓ How can you apply what you learned about Non-Verbal Communication in the videos to your Personal & Social life? Academic career? And the workplace? BE SPECIFIC!!!!
- ✓ Share your responses with the group and be prepared to present your responses to the class. Have the students hand in their written response for evaluation. (See Writing Rubric information Table#2.)

Assessment/Evaluation:

1. Discussion of videos small group and whole class
2. NonVerbal Communication worksheet
3. Student's written responses, use 10-point rubric
4. Group Work Evaluation form

Debriefing Conclusions:

1. Gestures have arbitrary cultural meaning; the same gesture can have different meanings in different cultures and different gestures can have the same meaning.
2. Dissonance in codes lead to misperception, misunderstanding, and confusion.
3. Unexpected reaction produces surprise and sense of discomfort.
4. Learning new codes is difficult.
5. Ask about gestures within the cultural context to avoid miscommunication.

Worksheet: Types of nonverbal communication

Facial Expressions
Hand & Body Gestures
Eye Contact
Body Postures
Personal Space

Writing Rubric information
10 POINT RUBRIC*

**What is a rubric? It is a scoring guide. It provides well-defined criteria from which learners can improve their performance.*

Level	Description
Outstanding Value:	Well written and very organized. Excellent grammar mechanics. Clear and concise statements. Excellent effort and presentation with detail. Demonstrates a thorough understanding of the topic. 9-10
Good Value:	Writes fairly clear. Good grammar mechanics. Good presentation and organization. Sufficient effort and detail. 7-8
Fair Value:	Minimal effort. Good grammar mechanics. Fair presentation. Few supporting details. 6
Poor Value:	Somewhat unclear. Shows little effort. Poor grammar mechanics. Confusing and choppy, incomplete sentences. No organization of thoughts. 4-5
Very Poor Value:	Lacking effort. Very poor grammar mechanics. Very unclear. Does not address topic. Limited attempt. 1-3

Group-Work Evaluation

Name _____ Group # _____

1. Overall, how effectively did your group work together on this assignment?

Poorly Adequately Well Very Well

2. Out of the four group members, how many participated actively most of the time?

None One Two Three All Four

3. Out of the four group members, how many were fully prepared for the activity?

None One Two Three All Four

4. Give one specific example of something you learned from the group that you probably wouldn't have learned working alone.

5. Give one specific example of something the other group members learned from you that they probably wouldn't have learned otherwise.

6. Suggest one change the group could make to improve its performance.

2.

Topic: Non-Verbal Intercultural Communication

Time Required: 50–120 minutes

Activity (Methodology): Pair work, mini simulation

Learning Objectives:

By the end of this lesson, students will be able to:

- List at least three different non-verbal communication styles.
- Express the importance of recognizing different verbal and non-verbal communication styles during interactions with others.

Materials:

- Computer with projector
- Printed materials for visualization
- White board with markers

Process:

Teacher divides students into groups of two. Be sure there is adequate open space for each pair to stand facing one another and without hitting or tripping over any objects during movement.

Directions:

1. Begin by asking students if they can define or provide an example of a communication style.
2. Explain that communication styles can be defined as: *The patterns of expression and rules for interaction that reflect the values and norms of a culture. They are generally described as continuum, with an understanding that no one person uses only one style for communicating or interacting at all times. One individual may rely heavily on one style or may adapt their use of these styles depending on the situation.*
3. Emphasize that this definition applies to both verbal and non-verbal means of communication (i.e., use of space, eye contact, touch, conversational turn-taking, body language, etc.)
4. Group students into groups of two and ask students to recall a difficult decision they once made and begin discussing this topic with their partner.
5. After roughly 15-30 seconds, without any further explanation, instruct students to continue the conversation while making direct and unwavering eye contact. Students should not look anywhere else.
6. After 15-20 seconds, next ask students to stop making eye contact and look away from their partner (i.e., at the floor, over their shoulder, etc.) while continuing the conversation. Students should not look their partner in the eye.
7. Continue this pattern of instructing to students to incorporate other non-verbal cues into their conversation at short intervals of 15-20 seconds each. In no specific order, consider including as many of the below styles as time permits and feel free to add in an additional topic in order for students to have information to talk about without stopping:

- ❖ **Physical Space** – Instruct students to stand about 1 ft. apart from each other while speaking, then instruct them to step back (approx. 5 feet) apart.
- ❖ **Physical Orientation** – Instruct students to continue speaking while one member of each pair turns around. One person should have their back to their partner, and the other person should be facing their partner's back.
- ❖ **Physical Touch** – Instruct students to continue the conversation while making some form of sustained physical contact (i.e., hand on the shoulder, holding hands, fist bump or high five...etc.)
- ❖ **Body Language** – Instruct students to speak while holding their arms crossed/folded at their chest, then with their hands on their hips.
- ❖ **Facial Expressions** – Instruct students to speak with as little expression as possible (i.e., flat affect- so smiling, frowning, crying...etc.)
- ❖ **Hand Gestures** – Instruct students to put their hands by their sides and continue the conversation without moving them or using any hand gestures. Then, reserve it and instruct them to use big, exaggerated hand gestures while speaking.
- ❖ **Turn Taking** – Instruct students to speak at the same time, interrupting each other often.
- ❖ **Speed of Speech** – Instruct students to speak quickly progressing to one thought to the next without any pauses, then very slowly perhaps with a lot of pauses and use of filler words (i.e., umm, so, uh, hmm... etc.)
- ❖ **Volume of Speech** – Instruct students to whisper their when they speak so as not to let others hear them, then follow it up by asking students to speak loudly with their partner.
- ❖ **Intonation of Speech** – Instruct students to speak with as little tone as possible in their voice (i.e., very flat- no ups and downs in pitch, accenting syllables, or questions... etc.). Then instruct students to speak as if each sentence were a question, regardless of if it is or isn't (i.e., the intonation should rise and get higher toward the end of each statement).

8. Once you have implemented all the listed styles, or as many as your timing allows, call the students back together for a large group discussion.

Discussion:

The goal of this lesson was to highlight that effective communication requires both verbal and non-verbal cues, and that various people (and cultures) may have different preferences. Consider asking students the following question to prompt discussion:

1. *How did it feel to interact in these ways?*
2. *What combinations were the most comfortable? The least comfortable? Why?*
3. *How and when do you adapt your preferences based on circumstances, if at all?*
4. *How might a lack of awareness of these styles be harmful?*
5. *How could you incorporate this new insight into your everyday interactions with others? How about with those from a different cultural background?*

Optional ways to conduct exercise:

Depending on how you incorporate this lesson plan into your content area you may wish to add a slight twist that more explicitly mirrors an encounter with someone who has different communication preferences. Begin the activity by first dividing the class into two groups— group 1 and group 2. Then instruct students to pair up with someone from the opposite group. Instead of having everyone follow the same instruction, instruct group 1 students to follow one instruction, and group 2 to follow the opposite instruction for each described style. For the few styles that do not have an opposite equivalent, the non-assigned pair should be instructed to speak as they usually would without rules or restrictions until the next instruction is given.

Alternatively, and space permitting, the teacher may also choose to forgo the pairs and have students engage in a larger group conversation, moving around the room and speaking with multiple people. In this scenario, be sure to add additional debrief questions regarding with whom they spent the most time or with whom were they the most comfortable speaking and why?

Materials for visualization:

 Offensive Gestures - The Five Fathers

It tells the other person that "They have five fathers" and that their mother is promiscuous.

Offensive in Arab and Caribbean countries

Offensive Gestures - A-OK Gesture

This is meant to symbolize a bodily orifice, and it's a way of calling them an a\$\$hole.

Offensive in Brazil

Offensive Gestures - The Moutza

The equivalent of a middle finger in the US. The most traditional insulting gesture among Greeks.

Offensive in Greece

Offensive Gestures - Inward-Facing Peace Sign

The equivalent of a middle finger in the US.

Offensive in US, UK, Ireland, Australia, and New Zealand

Offensive Gestures - The Fig Sign

In modern cultures, it is used to rudely deny a request.

Offensive across Western Europe, but mainly Turkish and Slavic cultures

Offensive Gestures - The Corna Sign

It's meant to convey cuckoldry or "I'm sleeping with your wife."

Offensive in Mediterranean and Latin countries like France, Brazil, Greece, Portugal, Spain, Mexico

Offensive Gestures - The Dog Call

Seen as a way to rudely beckon someone over - as fit only for dogs.

Offensive in the Philippines

Offensive Gestures - Crossing Your Fingers

It depicts women's genitalia. If pointed at someone, it's the same as calling them a c-word.

Offensive in Vietnam

Offensive Gestures - The Cutis

The equivalent of "screw you". It is meant not only to insult an individual but their entire family.

Offensive in India and Pakistan

Offensive Gestures - El Tacaño

People can also refer to a stingy person as "muy codo" which is literally calling someone an elbow.

Offensive in Mexico & South American Spanish-speaking countries

“V” for victory. Use this gesture with caution! While in North America it signs victory or peace, in England and Australia it means something closer to “take this!”

The “OK” gesture. While in North America it means things are going well, in France it means a person is thought to be worthless, in Japan it refers to money, and in Brazil, Russia, and Germany it means something really not appropriate for the workplace.

The *“thumbs up”* means one in Germany, five in Japan, but good job in North America. This can lead to confusion.

“Hook ‘em horns.” In Texas this is the University of Texas rallying call because it looks like the horns of a bull. However, in Italy it means you are being tricked, while in Brazil and Venezuela it means you are warding off evil.

Waving your hand. In much of Europe waving your hand indicates a disagreement. However, in North America it is routinely used as a way to signal greetings or to get someone’s attention.

3. "Imitation game" - Who is the candidate for the job?

Time Required: 120 minutes

Objectives:

1. Actively involve learners and create opportunities to communicate and use nonverbal communication in a situation they can relate to or are familiar with.
2. Define and interpret correctly nonverbal means of communication used by the candidates.

Materials:

- Board with markers
- Pen or pencil for each participant
- Handout with the description of the candidates (see Table 1)
- Candidate Assessment Form (see Table 2)

Process:

1. Elicit from students' nonverbal means of communication that are desirable for British, US, German, and French people; write the traits on the board. Make students work with Cultural Atlas:
<https://culturalatlas.sbs.com.au/countries>

Below is a list of nonverbal means according described cultures:

1.1. British culture

- ❖ **Expression:** The British do not always give away their emotions via facial expressions. For example, they may not show it if they have been offended. On the other hand, keeping a straight, serious face can be the punch line to many sarcastic jokes
- ❖ **Personal Space:** The British like to be given a fair amount of personal space, and may feel uncomfortable if someone sits or stands too close when other space is available. It is polite to maintain an arm's length distance between yourself and the person speaking.
- ❖ **Physical Contact:** British culture is generally quite reserved. People are generally comfortable touching those they know well (e.g. backslapping is common among close friends). However, women tend to be more physically affectionate with one another than men.
- ❖ **Gestures:** Gestures are usually quite reserved, polite and less demonstrative. For example, tapping the side of one's nose means that something is confidential or to be kept secret. It is considered offensive to make a V-sign with your index and middle finger, the palm facing inwards and the top of the hand facing the other person. This is another way of saying "up yours" in their culture. However, the V-sign with the palm facing outwards is understood as the sign for victory or peace.
- ❖ **Eye Contact:** It is best to make direct eye contact that breaks away now and again. Prolonged eye contact can make people feel uncomfortable, and staring is impolite. If talking to a group, be sure to make equal eye contact with all who are present.

1.2. American culture

- ❖ Eye Contact: Eye contact should be maintained directly. It demonstrates warmth, openness, honesty and approachability. If you make eye contact with a stranger in passing (on the street, at a shop, in a hallway, etc.) give a small smile or nod to acknowledge them. Continuing on your way without doing so means you were simply staring or unfriendly, and is considered slightly rude.
- ❖ Physical Contact: Generally, Americans are not very tactile outside of their families and close relationships. However, cities that are more internationally exposed may adopt more physical contact in their mannerisms. Touching someone of another gender – especially in the workplace – can be misinterpreted as sexual harassment.
- ❖ Personal Space: Americans like to be given a fair amount of personal space, so try not to encroach on it during a conversation. If an American feels you are ‘in their face’ too much, they will probably not mention it and simply step back.
- ❖ Gestures: It is best to nod or show some kind of sign that you are listening throughout a conversation.
- ❖ Smiling: Many Americans smile when passing strangers on the street as a simple gesture of goodwill.

1.3. German culture

- ❖ Personal Space: Germans usually keep about an arm’s length distance between one another when talking, and sometimes a little extra between men and women depending on how well they know each other. Standing too close to someone can be seen as an invasion of their privacy.
- ❖ Physical Contact: People tend not to touch one another very much during communication unless they are close friends. Touching someone on the shoulder or arm to emphasise a point is generally acceptable, but can otherwise be seen as a sexual advance. Women tend to be more physically affectionate with each other than men. It is polite to apologise if you accidentally bump into someone or make unwanted physical contact by saying “Entschuldigung” (Excuse me) in Germany.
- ❖ Eye Contact: Direct eye contact is expected, especially when speaking about a serious matter. It conveys sincerity and approachability. Avoiding eye contact may be seen as an indication of dishonesty or a lack of confidence. It is appropriate to break eye contact now and again as holding it for prolonged periods can make people uncomfortable. When talking to a group, be sure to make equal eye contact with all people present.
- ❖ Gestures: Touching your index finger to your thumb in a circle to demonstrate ‘Okay’ or ‘Good’ can be misunderstood. Instead of crossing the index finger and middle finger to indicate hoping for something or “Good Luck”, Germans squeeze the tip of their thumb between those two fingers (Daumendrücken). Letting one’s thumb protrude too far from between the fingers can be an obscene gesture, so only the tip should be visible.

- ❖ Pointing: Most Germans use their index finger to point, but some may use their little/pinkie finger.
- ❖ Expression: Some Germans may have quite a serious exterior upon first meeting people, reserving smiles for friends. Once they are familiar with someone, they generally become very animated.

1.4. French Culture

- ❖ Physical Contact: Touching during a conversation is accepted and considered a sign of affection only once you have reached a degree of familiarity. Young people will often engage in public displays of affection, such as embracing or kissing.
- ❖ Personal Space: An arm's length of distance or a bit closer is an appropriate amount of personal space.
- ❖ Eye Contact: Direct eye contact is understood as a form of respect. It is considered to be extremely rude not to make and maintain eye contact.
- ❖ Gestures: French people tend to use the 'thumbs up' sign to indicate 'okay'. Making a circle with the thumb and index finger means 'zero' in France.

2. Have students work individually or in small groups.

Tell students that they will form part of a committee that selects a candidate for a nongovernmental organization (NGO). Give to 4 students a handout with the description of the candidates (see Table 1) and the Candidate Assessment Form (see Table 2) to the rest of the group. Give time for the candidates to prepare, support them while the preparation. Circulate among students to answer questions later.

3. Let students fill in the assessment form in Table

4. In small groups, have students decide on a candidate and present their arguments for selecting him or her for the NGO position. The teacher and other students can ask further questions along the lines of the following:

- Does it make a difference if the job is done by a man or woman?
- How important is a person's age for this type of job?
- Would your choice have been influenced by knowing the people's names, especially names that hint at the person's ethnicity?

5. Provide feedback on nonverbal means of communication, those that were strong and those that can be improved.

6. Assign a written task or homework. Ask students to comment on the importance of nonverbal communication in general, or for a chosen profession.

Situation ASA is a nongovernmental organization that provides IELTS training.

Cards with description of the candidates

The organization is looking for someone who will provide skills training for the students to enable them to pass the exam successfully. The person should also know and work a lot with fulfilling the documents.

Candidate 1

You are a trained school teacher. You hold a certificate in art therapy (using art to overcome personal problems) and have implemented interesting school projects. You grew bored with her work at a school and decided to look for a job in another sector and another country. You are a lady from the USA, in your mid-30s and are an open-minded, creative, and assertive person.

(Use nonverbal means of communication to present your nationality, to support your speech within self-presentation, and try not to read the information given to you, the information given is only for you. Use nonverbal communication to support your strong sides, and try to use mimic codes of emotional states and prosody with extralinguistics to deliver the emotions connected to your personality)

Situation ASA is a nongovernmental organization that provides IELTS training. The organization is looking for someone who will provide skills training for the students to enable them to pass the exam successfully. The person should also know and work a lot with fulfilling the documents.

Candidate 2

You are male an English teacher from GB. You have just graduated from university and have completed an internship as an IELTS instructor. You have a

friendly, patient, and reliable personality but is a bit shy.

(Use nonverbal means of communication to present your nationality, to support your speech within self-presentation, and try not to read the information given to you, the information given is only for you. Use nonverbal communication to support your strong sides, and try to use mimic codes of emotional states and prosody with extra linguistics to deliver the emotions connected to your personality).

Situation ASA is a nongovernmental organization that provides IELTS training. The organization is looking for someone who will provide skills training for the students to enable them to pass the exam successfully. The person should also know and work a lot with fulfilling the documents.

Candidate 3

You are a male from France and are just under 30 years old. You don't have much experience as an IELTS instructor, but you've worked in various educational centres all over the world, before obtaining a philological degree. You have lived in difficult and even dangerous conditions in some cities and have been homeless for a short time. The candidate has a cheerful and lively personality and is committed to helping people. However, he does not seem very interested in the paperwork and the bureaucracy that form part of the job.

(Use nonverbal means of communication to present your nationality, to support your speech within self-presentation, and try not to read the information given to you, the information given is only for you. Use nonverbal communication to support your strong sides, and try to use mimic codes of emotional states and prosody with extra linguistics to deliver the emotions connected to your personality).

Situation ASA is a nongovernmental organization that provides IELTS training.

The organization is looking for someone who will provide skills training for the students to enable them to pass the exam successfully. The person should also know and work a lot with fulfilling the documents.

Candidate 4

You are female from Germany and you're in your 50s. You have many years of experience as an English teacher, particularly working with young people. You have changed jobs several times, mostly because she did not seem to get along with her bosses. You're an assertive person and take a strict attitude toward your students.

(Use nonverbal means of communication to present your nationality, to support your speech within self-presentation, and try not to read the information given to you, the information given is only for you. Use nonverbal communication to support your strong sides, and try to use mimic codes of emotional states and prosody with extra linguistics to deliver the emotions connected to your personality).

Table 2

Situation ASA is a nongovernmental organization that provides IELTS training. The organization is looking for someone who will provide skills training for the students to enable them to pass the exam successfully. The person should also know and work a lot with fulfilling the documents. Four people have been shortlisted for the job.

In your opinion where is the candidate from? Make a list of notes to prove the culture of the candidate according to his/her nonverbal behaviour.

CANDIDATE ASSESSMENT FORM

Assign points to each candidate by using the following scale:

- 1 – Meets all of the requirements**
- 2 – Meets most of the requirements**
- 3 – Meets some of the requirements**
- 4 – Does not meet any of the requirements**

Candidate 1

Educational /Background	Relevant Job/ Experience	Interpersonal/ Skills	Strengths/ Weaknesses	Comments on culture
1 2 3 4 Comments:	1 2 3 4 Comments:	1 2 3 4 Comments:		

Candidate 2

Educational /Background	Relevant Job/ Experience	Interpersonal/ Skills	Strengths/ Weaknesses	Comments on culture
1 2 3 4 Comments:	1 2 3 4 Comments:	1 2 3 4 Comments:		

Candidate 3

Educational /Background	Relevant Job/ Experience	Interpersonal/ Skills	Strengths/ Weaknesses	Comments on culture
1 2 3 4 Comments:	1 2 3 4 Comments:	1 2 3 4 Comments:		

Candidate 4

Educational /Background	Relevant Job/ Experience	Interpersonal/ Skills	Strengths/ Weaknesses	Comments on culture
1 2 3 4 Comments:	1 2 3 4 Comments:	1 2 3 4 Comments:		

Scientific advisor's report (Заклучение)

on the dissertation paper entitled "Nonverbal aspects of intercultural communication" by M.A. Saidova for academic MA degree in the specialty: 5A 111401 – Foreign languages and literature (The English Language)

Nonverbal communication can mean a lot of different things, and all of them are important in being an effective communicator. It is important to keep in mind the fact that cultural norms define a lot about nonverbal communication. Personal space, eye contact, and touching are just a few of the nonverbal tools that mean different things in different cultures. This MA thesis studies cultural-semantic peculiarities of nonverbal means used in the American and Russian linguocultures and offers special ways of teaching nonverbal means at English classes in the context of mastering communicative behaviour.

Structurally the research paper consists of an introduction, three chapters, outcomes of three chapters, a conclusion, the list of used literature and an appendix. Introduction includes all required research points and logic steps of their presentation.

Three chapters are interrelated and touch upon all sides of this problem. In particular the following matters are discussed: communicative and noncommunicative behaviours, variety of nonverbal means of communication, methodology of discovering semantic features of nonverbal means, cross-cultural analysis of nonverbal means, pragmatic difficulties in usage of nonverbal means and special technology of teaching nonverbal means at English classes.

The novel achievements in this work are 1) revealing the cultural features of some nonverbal means on the formal and functional levels of study; 2) working out the special technology of teaching non-verbal means at English classes and assessment tools. Without doubt, it is outstanding work in theoretical and applied plans.

The author used a lot of number of the state educational regulations and scientific literature in the English language which are relevant to the covered problems and published in the last decades. All of them are reflected in the text of dissertation. The paper is written in the literate English language, the style and the logic of the research are comprehensible and convincing.

Thus, the reviewing paper has topicality, scientific novelty, theoretical and practical value. Findings of the research are objective and proved by experimental way. The results of research can be used by teachers and researches.

The paper has been completed quite independently and can be recommended to the public defense.

Scientific advisor

D.S., prof. G. Makhkamova, TSPU